

The Saturday Office of Our Lady in Medieval Portugal

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Abstract

This article examines the Saturday Office of Our Lady in the liturgical uses of medieval Portugal through the analysis of manuscripts and early printed breviaries associated with Braga, Coimbra, Évora, and related sources. It reconstructs the structure, textual contents, and chant repertoires of the surviving offices, including the expansion from a three- to a nine-lesson form, and situates selected textual and chant material within broader Iberian and European traditions. Particular attention is given to the use of patristic and homiletic texts as well as miracle narratives. Comparative analysis reveals complex patterns of internal and external borrowing and adaptation involving Marian feasts, the daily Hours of the Virgin, the ferial office, and regional liturgical traditions. The study argues that these offices emerged through intersecting processes of transmission that combined shared repertorial materials with distinct local configurations shaped by evolving liturgical and devotional contexts.

Introduction

From the late tenth century onwards, liturgical offices expressing Marian devotion were disseminated across Continental Europe and the British Isles.¹ Two principal types of such offices are attested: the daily Hours of the Virgin (*Officium Parvum de BMV*, the Little Office) and the commemorative Saturday Office of Our Lady (*Officium Sanctae Mariae in Sabbato*). Both are accretions to the Divine Office. The daily Hours of the Virgin run parallel to the weekly cursus. Evolving from simple memorials or suffrages, they include all eight canonical hours, starting with Matins in a three-lesson form with three psalms, and commonly accommodate seasonal or alternating daily variations. Their first known examples date from the eleventh century.² Although initially associated with private devotion, the daily Hours were progressively integrated into communal liturgical observance, before returning to private use through the diffusion of books of hours in the later Middle Ages. Books of hours often

¹ On the early history of Marian offices, see E. Bishop, 'On the Origin of the Prymer', in *Liturgica Historica: Papers on the Liturgy and Religious Life of the Western Church* (Oxford, 1918), pp. 211-37, at pp. 224-8; J. M. Canal, 'Oficio parvo de la Virgen: Formas viejas y formas nuevas', *Ephemerides Mariologicae*, 11 (1961), pp. 497-525; J. M. Canal, 'El Oficio parvo de la Virgen de 1000 a 1250', *Ephemerides Mariologicae*, 15 (1965), pp. 463-75; M. Clayton, *The Cult of the Virgin Mary in Anglo-Saxon England* (Cambridge, 1990), pp. 65-81; K. Ihnat, *Mother of Mercy, Bane of the Jews: Devotion to the Virgin Mary in Anglo-Norman England* (Princeton and Oxford, 2016), pp. 32-9; J. Leclercq, 'Formes successives de l'Office votif de la Vierge', *Ephemerides Liturgicae*, 72 (1958), pp. 294-301; J. Leclercq, 'Formes anciennes de l'Office marial', *Ephemerides Liturgicae*, 74 (1960), pp. 89-102; S. E. Roper, 'Medieval English Benedictine Liturgy: Studies in the Formation, Structure, and Content of the Monastic Votive Office, c. 950-1540', 2 vols. (PhD thesis, Brasenose College, Oxford, 1988), vol. 1, especially pp. 118-99, later published in one volume under the same title (New York and London, 1993); page references are to the original thesis, available at <<https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:639874f5-7097-4ee1-a282-4dd82003c309>>; and A. B. Yardley, 'Commemorating the Virgin Mary at Barking Abbey: Cambridge, University Library, Dd.12.56', *Plainsong and Medieval Music*, 32/1 (2023), pp. 67-90.

² See, for instance, *Facsimiles of Horae de Beata Maria Virgine from English Mss. of the Eleventh Century*, ed. E. S. Dewick (London, 1902) and Leclercq, 'Formes anciennes'.

created hybrid offices by inserting items from one use into the established cursus of another.³ In many uses, the Saturday Office of Our Lady replaces the office assigned for the day. It is usually omitted during certain seasons, most often Advent, Lent, and Eastertide, although in several cases it also accommodates seasonal variations. Feasts of higher rank or with a proper office normally take precedence over it, in which case it may be anticipated to Friday or even Thursday in some uses. In contrast to the daily Hours, it typically, though not always, begins with First Vespers. Its first known examples also date from the eleventh century and adopt the three-lesson form.⁴ From the twelfth century onwards, a nine-lesson form with nine psalms developed from the three-lesson form, which nevertheless continued to be used in many churches.⁵

The existing literature has tended to focus primarily on the daily Office of the Virgin, while the Saturday Office has received comparatively less attention. Some studies, however, fail to distinguish clearly between the two types of office.⁶ In addition, research on Marian liturgical offices has been disproportionately concentrated on British sources, whereas Continental traditions remain understudied.⁷ This work seeks to contribute to filling part of this gap, building on Solange Corbin's pioneering study.⁸

1. Braga, Coimbra, and related sources

The first known reference in Portugal to a commemorative Office of Our Lady on Saturdays appears in a charter of donation issued in January 1200 by Pedro Salvado, a canon and

³ See D. Stutzmann and L. Chevalier, 'Books of hours as codified compilations of compilations: Textual networks and hybrid liturgical uses', *Journal of Historical Network Research*, 9 (2023), pp. 130-83, at pp. 161-77.

⁴ See, for instance, Roper, 'Medieval English Benedictine Liturgy', vol. 1, pp. 160-2, and vol. 2, p. 67.

⁵ In England particularly, the one-nocturn form with three lessons and three psalms does not seem to have prevailed. Instead, in the thirteenth century, the monastic two-nocturn form with three lessons and twelve psalms largely superseded the three-nocturn festal form with twelve lessons; see Roper, 'Medieval English Benedictine Liturgy', vol. 1, pp. 156-60.

⁶ Two examples, among others, may be cited. The nine-lesson office in *F-Pn* lat. 3719, fols. 93^r-100^v, under the title 'In veneratione beatae Mariae', occupies a thirteenth-century component unit of this composite manuscript from Saint-Martial de Limoges. Comprising only Matins and Lauds, it is probably best understood as the fragment of a votive office rather than a form of the daily Hours, as published in Canal, 'Oficio parvo de la Virgen'. The same may be said of the nine-lesson office in *F-Pn* lat. 10433 (the late twelfth-century Westminster Psalter), fols. 226^r-249^v, comprising a complete cursus from Matins to Compline, together with appended masses 'De sancto spiritu' and 'De sancta Maria', published in Canal, 'Oficio parvo de la Virgen'.

⁷ As the literature referred to in n. 1 above clearly indicates. Although not concerned with early forms of the daily Hours, one further study on a Continental use should also be cited: R. A. Baltzer, 'The Little Office of the Virgin and Mary's Role at Paris', in *The Divine Office in the Latin Middle Ages: Methodology and Source Studies, Regional Developments, Hagiography*, ed. M. E. Fassler and R. A. Baltzer (Oxford, 2000), pp. 463-84. For a comprehensive study of the Hours of the Virgin, see R. F. Brown, *Mary and the Art of Prayer: The Hours of the Virgin in Medieval Christian Life and Thought* (New York, 2018).

⁸ S. Corbin, *Essai sur la musique religieuse portugaise au Moyen Âge (1100-1385)* (Paris, 1952), pp. 350-74.

chaplain of Coimbra Cathedral, who had purchased five properties for the purpose of rewarding those who attended the said office.⁹ The relevant passage reads as follows:¹⁰

[...] illis qui venerint ad horas Sancte Marie celebrandum, in illis sabbatis quibus licet fieri commemoratio ejus, sint tantum ad subsidium, hoc modo:
omnes fructus, ex prescriptis hereditatibus provenientes, vendatur et pro numis commutentur.
Ipsi autem numi in tres partes dividantur: quarum una detur illis qui venerint ad vespervas predictae commemorationis; et qui venerint ad matutinas, que debent celebrari cum novem leccionibus, aliam partem habeant;
illis vero qui venerint ad missam maiorem, pars tertia detur.
Sed cum discretione provideatur ut, eodem modo et numero quo ministratum fuerit illis in primo sabbato, eodem, per totum annum, in sequentibus ministretur.
Et per singulos annos, secundum quantitatem vel valorem fructuum, fiat ita trium dispensatio partium;
ad hoc enim ipsas hereditates comparavi, ad hoc mee devotionis in hoc propositum fuit, quatinus ad honorem Dei et Beate Marie semper Virginis jam dictum subsidium ex eis persolvatur.

[...] those who come to celebrate the Hours of Saint Mary, on the Saturdays when her commemoration is permitted, shall receive only a subsidy, in the following manner:
all the produce from the previously described properties shall be sold and converted into money.
This money shall be divided into three parts: one part shall be given to those who attend Vespers of the said commemoration; another part shall go to those who attend Matins, which are to be celebrated with nine lessons;
and the third part shall be given to those who attend the principal Mass.
Care shall be taken, however, that the same manner and amount of distribution made on the first Saturday be observed in the following Saturdays throughout the year.
And each year, according to the quantity or value of the produce, the division of the three parts shall be made in the same way;
for I purchased these properties for this very purpose, and my devotion was directed to this end: that, in honour of God and of the Blessed Mary ever Virgin, the said subsidy may be paid from them.

However, this office cannot yet be securely identified in any surviving source. The earliest extant witness to the Braga three-lesson form of the Saturday Office of Our Lady – commonly referred to as *Cantica Canticorum* – is found in the Braga breviary known as the ‘Soeiro Breviary’, copied in the late fourteenth or early fifteenth century from an exemplar dating to around 1340, under the rubric ‘In solemn commemoratione beatae virginis quae ut infra notatur quolibet sabbato ab octavis pentecostes usque ad primam dominicam adventus domini nisi festum novem lectionum ibi occurrerit vel sint octavae alicuius festivitatis solemnem processionem habentis debet more bracharensis ecclesiae celebrari’ (‘On the solemn commemoration of the Blessed Virgin, which, as noted below [in the general rules], is to be

⁹ ‘Karta donationis illorum qui venerint ad Horas Sancte Marie in Sabbatis sue commemorationis’ (‘Charter of donation for those who attend the Hours of Saint Mary on the Saturdays of her commemoration’), in *P-Lant Cabido da Sé de Coimbra*, liv. 6, *Liber inventarius cartarum sive testamentorum*, known as ‘Livro preto’, fols. 226^v-227^r. I thank Manuel Pedro Ferreira for bringing this document to my attention.

¹⁰ Transcription of the original Latin by M. A. Rodrigues, *Livro Preto: Cartulário da Sé de Coimbra* (Coimbra, 1999), doc. 589, pp. 789-90.

celebrated every Saturday from the Octave of Pentecost until the First Sunday of Advent, unless a feast of nine lessons occurs then, or it falls within the octave of some feast having a solemn procession, it shall be celebrated according to the use of the Church of Braga’).¹¹ The breviary known as the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’, likely copied in 1478, but representing the breviary in use between 1450 and 1470, still contains it.¹² Although classified as ‘solemn’, it is a three-lesson office, arranged as shown in Table 1 below, which is based on the reading of the ‘Soeiro Breviary’.¹³

Ad Vesperas	
A	Gaude Maria virgo (002924) PS Confitebor (137) PS Domine probasti (138) PS Eripe me (139) PS Domine clamavi (140) PS Voce mea (141) [E-E e-IV-10 same antiphon] PS Confitebor ii ^o cum aliis quatuor sequentibus.
cap	Beata es Maria quae dominum portasti ... permanes virgo. (Same text as R 006163)
H	Ave maris stella (008272)
W	Elegit eam deus (008046.2)
M	Ave regina caelorum (001542.1)
or	Concede nos famulos tuos ... perfrui laetitia.
rubr	Post haec fiat commemoratio de cruce deinde de omnibus sanctis postea de pace. [E-E e-IV-10 same rubric ending] et de pace.
Ad Matutinum	
I	Ave Maria gratia plena dominus tecum benedicta tu in mulieribus (001042) PS Venite (94)
H	Quem terra pontus (008375)
In noct.	

¹¹ P-BRad Ms. 657, fols. 320^v-321^r; P. R. Rocha, *L’Office Divin au Moyen Âge dans l’Église de Braga: Originalité et dépendances d’une liturgie particulière au Moyen Âge* (Paris, 1980), pp. 305-6. As is clear from the initial rubric, the Saturday Office of Our Lady was subject to seasonal restrictions and to rules of precedence. These seasonal restrictions, precedence rules, and liturgical ranking were adjusted over time up to the 1549 breviary – *Breuiarium bracarense* (Braga: João Álvares and João Barreira, 1549) – where a comprehensive prefatory rubric (fols. 92^v-93^v) details these matters. The nature and circumstances of these adjustments are explained in J. A. Ferreira, *Estudos histórico-litúrgicos: Os ritos particulares das Igrejas de Braga e Toledo* (Coimbra, 1924), pp. 145-51, and Corbin, *Essai*, pp. 365-7.

¹² E-E e-IV-10, fols. 91^v-93^r. This breviary, although of the Braga use, may have some connection with the city of Porto; see P. R. Rocha, ‘Um breviário bracarense na Biblioteca do Escorial’, *Lusitania Sacra*, 9 (1970), pp. 41-54, at pp. 53-4, and, on the copying date, pp. 42 and 52-3. However, the series of responsories for the Office of the Dead, on fols. 89^r-91^v, immediately before the three-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum*, follows the use of Évora as attested in its 1528 printed breviary, *Breuiarium secundum consuetudinem sancte Elborensis ecclesie* (Seville: Jacob Cromberger, 1528) [*Évora brev.*].

¹³ Differences with the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’ are indicated in Table 1. The initial rubric in this latter breviary, though identical in content, has a different formulation: ‘Incipit cantica canticorum et dicitur in sabbato quando fit de virginem. Quolibet sabbato ab octavis penthecostes usque ad primam dominica adventus domini, in festum novem leccionum vel tum occurrerit ibi vel sint octave alicum festivitatis sollempnem processionem habentis, vel sit vigilia alicum festi proprias lectiones habentis, debet more ecclesiae bracharensis sic celebrari’ (‘The [office] *Cantica Canticorum* begins, and it is said on Saturday when the Virgin is celebrated. Every Saturday from the Octave of Pentecost until the First Sunday of Advent, if a feast of nine lessons occurs then, or if it falls within the octave of some feast having a solemn procession, or if it is the vigil of some feast having its own lessons, it is to be celebrated in this manner according to the use of the Church of Braga’). Chant pieces are always identified with their Cantus ID the first time they are referred to in the main text. Biblical references follow the *Biblia Sacra Vulgata*, ed. R. Weber and R. Gryson, 5th ed. (Stuttgart, 2007).

A	Gaude Maria virgo (002924) PS Cantate domino canticum novum quia mirabilia (97) et cetera cum aliis praedictis psalmis sequentibus qui sabbato solent dici. [E-E e-IV-10, same antiphon] PS Cantate domino ii° cum aliis consueti psalmis sequentibus ut in sabbato solent dici.
W	Speciosa facta es et suavis R. In deliciis tuis sancta dei genitrix (008202)
rubr	<i>Benedictiones dicantur prout supra in alio tempore die sabbati ordinantur. Tres lectiones legantur de canticis canticorum quae inferius annotantur. Tria vero responsoria dicantur de infra subsequuntur.</i> [E-E e-IV-10 same rubric ending] <i>Tres lectiones legatur de canticis canticorum quae hic notatur.</i> [Nine lessons from Greg. Epithalamium 1:1-2, 4-7 follow, after which the rubric resumes:] <i>Tria vero Responsoria dicantur quorum principia hic subsequuntur.</i>
R1	Stirps Jesse (007709)
V1	Virgo dei genitrix (007709a)
R2	Ad nutum domini (006024)
V1	Ut vitium virtus (006024a)
R3	Candida virginitas (006262)
V1	Quae meruit dominum (006262a)
V2	Gloria (909000) [not in E-E e-IV-10]
rubr	[E-E e-IV-10] <i>Quo tertio Responsorio cantato dicitur</i>
TD	Te deum laudamus (909010)
rubr	[E-E e-IV-10] <i>Et in fine dicitur</i>
W	[E-E e-IV-10] Ora pro nobis sancta dei genitrix (800319)
In Laudibus	
A	Sub tuam protectionem (005040) PS Dominus regnavit (92) cum aliis consuetis
cap	Ego quasi vitis ... fructus honoris et honestatis. (Eccles. 24:23)
H	O gloriosa domina (008375e.1)
W	Elegit eam deus (008046.2)
B	Anima mea liquefacta est (001418)
or	Concede nos famulos tuos ut supra
rubr	<i>Deinde commemoretur de cruce et de omnibus sanctis et de pace. Ad primam vero tertiam sextam et nonam dicantur omnia ut supra in alio primo tempore sunt notata.</i> [E-E e-IV-10 same rubric ending] <i>omnia ut infra notatur in officio eiusdem virginis quod celebrantur a festo purificationis usque dominica in passione et a sequenti die post festum sancte trinitatis usque ad adventum domini. Responsoria superposita quaere in nativitate eiusdem beatae mariae.</i>

Table 1. The three-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum*.

This office has no Compline or Second Vespers and employs the same single antiphon for the psalms in both Vespers and Matins, these being the ferial psalms, as in Lauds. The antiphons for Vespers, Matins, and Lauds are drawn from the two lists prescribed for the days within the octave of the Assumption in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’, the second of which, including the canticle antiphons, is also to be used, if necessary, on the Nativity of the Blessed Virgin, as well as in her commemorations both solemn and simple – ‘si necesse fuerit Nativitatis beatae virginis in commemorationibus eiusdem tam sollempnibus quam aliis simplicibus’.¹⁴ As Pedro Romano Rocha notes, the first twelve antiphons in the first list, the one intended for use within the octave ‘ad nocturnos et ad vespas’, correspond to the Cluniac series for Matins of the

¹⁴ P-BRad Ms. 657, fols. 255^v-256^r.

Assumption.¹⁵ Rocha also draws attention, with some surprise, to the fact that the chapter of Vespers is not taken from Scripture, as is customary, but rather consists of the text of a widely disseminated responsory (006163), most commonly assigned to the Assumption.¹⁶ This text as a chapter, however, occurs in a number of English uses, assigned to Vespers, Lauds or Terce of the daily Hours of the Virgin,¹⁷ and appears to have also been well distributed across France and the Iberian Peninsula.¹⁸

In 1431, the Provincial Synod of Braga, convened by Archbishop Fernando da Guerra, ordered that the earlier three-lesson office be replaced by a nine-lesson form. This nine-lesson office was also entered into the ‘Soeiro Breviary’ as an addition following the *regulae generales*, with most of its items reduced to their incipits.¹⁹ As will become clear from Table 2 below, which outlines the nine-lesson office based on the more complete reading in the mid-fifteenth-century Braga breviary known as the ‘Valasco Breviary’,²⁰ it results from the expansion of the earlier three-lesson office. The long rubric that precedes it reads as follows:

Officium beatae virginis.

Sciendum est quod anno a nativitate domini millesimo quatorcentesimo tricesimo primo in generali sinodo statutum fuit per dominum fernandum archiepiscopum et capitulum

Office of the Blessed Virgin.

It is to be known that, in the year of the Nativity of the Lord one thousand four hundred and thirty-one, at a general synod, it was established by lord Fernando, Archbishop, and the chapter

¹⁵ Rocha, *L'Office Divin*, pp. 260-1, nn. 445 and 446. As also observed by Rocha, similar lists occur in the antiphoner *E-Tc* Ms. 44.2, though not including the Magnificat antiphon *Ave regina caelorum*.

¹⁶ Rocha, *L'Office Divin*, p. 301, n. 503.

¹⁷ See, for instance, *The Monastic Breviary of Hyde Abbey, Winchester: Mss. Rawlinson liturg. e. 1**, and *Gough liturg. 8, in the Bodleian Library, Oxford*, ed. J. B. L. Tolhurst, vol. 5 (London, 1934), fols. 446^r-447^r; *The Prymer or Lay Folks' Prayer Book (with several facsimiles) from the MS. Dd. 11, 82, ab. 1420-30 A.D., in the Library of the University of Cambridge*, ed. H. Littlehales, Part 2: *Introduction* (London, 1895), pp. 85-6, transcribing *GB-Lbl* MS. Harl. 1804 (use of Durham, fifteenth century); and *F-Pn* lat. 10433, fol. 241^v (use of Westminster, late twelfth century).

¹⁸ The following examples suffice to illustrate this: *F-Pn* lat. 13239, breviary, use of Saint-Germain-des-Prés, fourteenth century, fol. 510^v; *F-Psg* Ms. 2630, breviary, use of Saint-Lô de Rouen, second half of the fifteenth century, fol. 331^r; *Breviarium ad usum Ecclesiae Lascurrensis* (Lescar: Jacques Colomiès, 1541), ed. V. Dubarat as *Le Bréviaire de Lescar de 1541* (Paris, 1891), p. 230; *Breviarium Compostellanum* (Lisbon: Nicolau de Saxónia, 1497), fols. [Jiiij]^r and Kij^v; *Breviarium Toletanum* (Venice: Johann Hamman, 1492) [*Toledo brev.*], fols. 184^r and 184^v; *F-Pn* lat. 982, breviary, use of Seville, third quarter of the fifteenth century (c.1462), fols. 185^v and 186^f. In the French sources, this chapter is assigned to Vespers (or Prime, in the case of Lescar) of the daily Hours of the Virgin. In the Iberian sources, it is also assigned to Vespers of the Saturday office, as in Braga.

¹⁹ *P-BRad* Ms. 657, fol. 176^{r-v}; Rocha, *L'Office Divin*, pp. 206-7. Only the First Vespers Magnificat antiphon, the *Nunc dimittis* antiphon, the Invitatory antiphon, and the second responsory of the second nocturn, *Virginibus cunctis*, none of which are found elsewhere in the manuscript, are given in full.

²⁰ *GB-Ob* Ms. Lat. Liturg. e.12, fols. 342^r-344^v. On this breviary, dated to after 1431 and before 1455, see M. P. Ferreira, ‘Liturgia bracarense: Origens, fontes, posteridade’, in *O Clero secular medieval e as suas catedrais: Novas perspectivas e abordagens*, ed. A. M. S. Saraiva and M. R. B. Morujão (Lisbon, 2014), pp. 123-40, at p. 134, n. 19. Differences with the ‘Soeiro Breviary’, *P-BRad* Ms. 657, the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’, *E-E* e-IV-10, and the 1494 printed breviary of Braga – *Breviarium bracharense* (Braga: Johann Gherlinc, 1494) [*Braga brev.*] – are indicated in Table 2; PL stands for *Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Latina*, ed. J.-P. Migne, 221 vols. (Paris, 1844-1865).

ecclesiae bracharensis [quod in dicta ecclesia]²¹
et in ecclesiis cathedralibus subfraganeis
eiusdem ecclesiae bracharensis et in ecclesiis et
monasteriis eorumdem.

Omnes dies sabbati ut a festo sanctae trinitatis
usque ad adventum domini fiant novem
lectiones ad honorem beatissimae virginis
mariae exceptis dupplicibus festis.

Et si infra hoc tempus vigilia alicuius sancti
evenerit quae proprias habeant lectiones ultima
lectio fiat de vigilia.

Et proceditur hoc modo.

of the church of Braga [that in the said church]
and in the cathedral churches suffragan to the
same church of Braga, and in the churches and
monasteries belonging to them,

on all Saturdays, from the feast of the Holy
Trinity until the Advent of the Lord, nine
lessons be held in honour of the most blessed
Virgin Mary, except on double feasts.

And if, during this period, a vigil of any saint
occurs which has proper lessons, the last lesson
shall be taken from the vigil.

And it proceeds in this manner.

Ad Vesperas	
rubr	<i>Feria sexta super psalmos</i>
A	Gaude Maria virgo (002924) <i>psalmi feriales</i>
cap	Beata es Maria quae dominum portasti ... permanes virgo. (Same text as R 006163)
H	Ave maris stella (008272)
W	Elegit eam deus (008046.2)
M	Speciosa facta es et suavis (206209)
or	Concede nos famulos tuos
rubr	[P-BRad Ms. 657] <i>Postea fiat commemoratio de cruce et de omnibus sanctis et de pace.</i> [E-E e-IV-10] <i>Ut sicut in alio tempore, postea fiat commemoratio de cruce et de omnibus</i> <i>sanctis et de pace.</i> [Braga brev.] <i>Deinde fiat commemoratio de cruce et de omnibus sanctis et de pace ut supra.</i>
[Ad Completorium]	
N	Glorificamus te dei genitrix (002952)
rubr	[E-E e-IV-10] <i>Oratio et omnia alia dicantur more consueto.</i>
[Ad Matutinum]	
I	In honore beatissimae Mariae virginis jubilemus domino (001086) [PS Venite] (94)
H	Quem terra pontus (008375)
In I noct.	
A1.1	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709) PS Domine dominus noster (8)
A1.2	Sicut myrrha electa (004942) PS Caeli enarrant (18)
A1.3	Haec est quae nescivit (003001) PS Domini est terra (23)
W	Benedicta tu in mulieribus R. Et benedictus (007971)
rubr	<i>Benedictiones dicantur pro ut supra in alio tempore diei sabbati sunt ordinate. Tres</i> <i>lectiones legantur de canticis canticorum quorum hic sequitur.</i> <i>Incipit epitolanicum [sic] gregorii papae urbis romae libri in cantica canticorum.</i> [not in P-BRad Ms. 657] [E-E e-IV-10] <i>Sex lectiones legantur de cantica canticorum. Tres vero ultimae lectiones</i> <i>legantur de homilia beati jheronimi presbiteri quae incipiunt Maximae devotionis.</i> [No rubric in the Braga brev.]

²¹ The scribe inadvertently omitted a line of text, here restored from the reading found in the mid-fifteenth-century breviary formerly held in the old Archiepiscopal Archive, later the property of the Dukes of Palmela, subsequently acquired in 1972 by Avelino de Jesus da Costa from the antiquarian Albrecht Rosenthal in Oxford, and now in P-BRs s.s. The eighteenth-century Oratorian liturgist António Pereira de Figueiredo, who studied this breviary, calls it 'de letra miúda' ('in small script'), though it is now known as the 'Duques de Palmela Breviary'; see A. P. Figueiredo, *Dissertação Crítica sobre o antigo e moderno Calendário Bracaraense, para servir de Plano à emenda e reformação que no Breviário e Missal da mesma Santa Igreja medita fazer o Sereníssimo Senhor D. Gaspar, Arcebispo Primaz*, autograph, Lisbon, 1770, revised 1781, P-Lac Ms. 259 Azul, fol. 30r; fair copies in P-EVp Mss CXI/2-14 and CXII/2-16.

lect. 1	Audistis epitolamicum [<i>sic</i>] carmen ... id est deus et homo. (Greg. <i>Epithalamium</i> , 1:1) [not in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Osculetur me osculo ... propter vocem sponsi. (Greg. <i>Epithalamium</i> , 1:1)
R1.1	Stirps Jesse (007709)
V1	Virgo dei genitrix (007709a)
lect. 2	Sponsum autem Christum ... in fide et caritate. (Ibid.) [not in <i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657 or in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Et alius propheta ... meliora melioribus nuncupantur. (Greg. <i>Epithalamium</i> , 1:1-2)
R1.2	Ad nutum domini (006024)
V1	Ut vitium virtus (006024a)
lect. 3	Denique ut sciatis ... et ceteri cecinerunt. (Id. 1:2) [not in <i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657 or in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Cum ergo dicit ... ei osculum dabat. (Greg. <i>Epithalamium</i> , 1:4)
R1.3	Candida virginitas (006262)
V1	Quae meruit dominum (006262a)
In II noct.	
A2.1	Speciosa facta es (004988) PS Eructavit cor (44)
A2.2	Dignare me laudare (002217) PS Deus noster refugium (45)
A2.3	Sicut laetantium (004936) PS Fundamenta (86)
W	Sicut myrrha electa (008197)
lect. 4	Osculetur me osculo oris sui ... introduxit me rex in cellaria sua. (Cant. 1:1-3a) [not in <i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657 or in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Haec ergo ecclesia ... per Jesum Christum facta est. (Greg. <i>Epithalamium</i> , 1:5-6)
R2.1	Virginis electae (602499.1)
V1	Coetus caelorum (602499.1a)
lect. 5	Exsultabimus et laetabimur ... sicut pelles Salomonis. (Cant. 1:3b-4) [not in <i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657 or in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Ecclesia enim ut apostolos ... de matre virgine nata [<i>sic</i>] est. (Greg. <i>Epithalamium</i> , 1:7)
R2.2	Virginibus cunctis genitrix (602498.1)
V1	Cuius ventre deus jacuit (602498a)
lect. 6	Nolite me considerare ... quem diligit animam [meam.] (Cant. 1:5-6a) [not in <i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657 or in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Cuius origo terrena est ... per anulum fidei est adimpletum. (Greg. <i>Epithalamium</i> , 1:7-8)
R2.3	Hortus conclusus (601080)
V1	Fons hortorum puteus (601080a)
In III noct.	
A3.1	Oculi tui sancta dei genitrix (004110) PS Cantate domino i° (95)
A3.2	Post partum virgo (004332) PS Dominus regnavit (96)
A3.3	Gaude Maria virgo (002924) PS Cantate ii° (97)
W	[<i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657 and <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] Speciosa (008202) [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Specie tua (008201)
lect. 7	<i>Secundum lucham</i> In illo tempore Loquente Jesu ad turbas: extollens vocem ... et ubera quae suxisti (Luke 11:27). Et reliqua. <i>Omelia bede presbiteri de eadem lectione</i> [<i>Braga brev.</i>] <i>Omelia Origenis.</i> Magnae devotionis et fidei haec mulier ostenditur ... confundat haeticorum perfidiam. (Bede, <i>In Lucae Evangelio Expositio</i> , IV, PL 92:479) [<i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657 lacks the incipit of Bede's homily; only the rubric is given] [<i>E-E</i> e-IV-10 lacks the lemma; only the following rubric is given] <i>Tres ultimae lectiones legantur de Omelia quae incipiunt Maximae devotionis, Ut supra.</i>
R3.1	Ave festiva feruli (600178)

V1	Monte Libano (600178a)
lect. 8	Nam sicut tunc Judei ... carnis sui materiam ministrasse. (Ibid.) [not in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Nam sicut tunc Judei ... non debere dixerunt. (Ibid.)
R3.2	Virga dedit florem (a00365)
V1	Gaudeat omnis homo (a00365a)
lect. 9	Verum consubstantialemque ... ubera quae eum lactassent beneficerentur. (Ibid.) [not in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Sed si caro verbi dei ... uterque liquor emanare probatur. (Ibid.)
R3.3	Felix valde es (600873.1) [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Felix namque es (006725)
V1	Ora pro clero (600873b) [not in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] Ora pro clero (006725b)
TD	[<i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657, <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10, and <i>Braga brev.</i>] Te deum laudamus (909010)
W	Ora pro nobis R. Ut digni (800319)
In Laudibus	
A1	Sub tuam protectionem (005040) PS Dominus regnavit (92) <i>cum aliis consuetis</i> [<i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657] <i>cum ceteris de laudibus</i> [No indication of the other psalms in <i>E-E</i> e-IV-10 and the <i>Braga brev.</i>]
A2	Hortus conclusus (003137.1)
A3	Sancta dei genitrix (004699.1)
A4	In odorem unguentorum (003261)
A5	Sub tuum praesidium (005041)
cap	Ego quasi vitis ... fructus honoris et honestatis. (Eccles. 24:23)
H	O gloriosa domina (008375e.1)
W	Elegit eam deus (008046.2)
B	Ave spes nostra dei genitrix (001546)
or	Concede nos famulos tuos
rubr	<i>Per horas diei antiphonae de laudibus.</i> [<i>P-BRad</i> Ms. 657] <i>Deinde fiat commemoratio de cruce et de omnibus sanctis et de pace. Ad horas diei antiphonae de laudibus. Capitula versiculo et Responsorialia ad iij. vj. ix. dicantur ut in commemoratione. Ad vespers antiphonae de i° et ii° nocturno</i> PS Dixit dominus PS Laudate pueri PS Laetatus sum PS Nisi dominus PS Lauda Jerusalem [No further indications for the Lesser Hours; the text resumes with the incipit of the chapter for Second Vespers.] [<i>E-E</i> e-IV-10] <i>Deinde fiat commemoratio de cruce et de omnibus sanctis et de pace. Per horas diei antiphonae de laudibus. ad primam tertiam sextam nonam dicantur omnia ut in primo tempore.</i> [No further indications for the Lesser Hours.] [<i>Braga brev.</i>] <i>Deinde commemoretur de cruce et de omnibus sanctorum et de pace. cetera dicantur ad horas diei ut sicut in aliis horis post festum purifi[cationis] beatae virginis.</i> [No further indications for the Lesser Hours.]
Ad Tertiam	
cap	Ab initio et ante saecula ... coram ipso ministravi. (Eccles. 24:14)
R	Ora pro nobis sancta dei genitrix (601702)
V1	Ut digni efficiamur gloria Christi (601702a)
V2	Gloria patri (909000)
W	Benedicta tu in mulieribus R. Et benedictus fructus ventris tuis (007971)
Ad Sextam	
cap	Et sic in Sion firmata ... in Jerusalem potestas mea. (Eccles. 24:15)
R	Speciosa facta es et suavis (602225)
V1	In deliciis tuis sancta dei genitrix (602225a)
V2	Gloria patri (909000)
W	Sicut myrrha electa odorem dedisti R. Suavitatis sancta dei genitrix (008197)
or	Concede nos
Ad Nonam	
cap	Et radicavi in populo ... sanctorum detentio mea. (Eccles. 24:16)
R	Elegit eam deus et praelegit eam (600764)

V1	In tabernaculo suo habitare eam facit (600764c)
V2	Gloria patri (909000)
W	Speciosa facta es R. In deliciis (008202.1)
Ad II Vesperas	
rubr	[E-E e-IV-10 only] <i>In commemoratione beatae virginis in secundis vespis.</i>
A1	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709) PS Dixit dominus (109)
A2	Sicut myrrha electa (004942) PS Laudate pueri (112)
A3	Haec est quae nescivit (003001) PS Laetatus sum (121)
A4	Speciosa facta es (004988) PS Nisi dominus (126)
A5	Dignare me laudare (002217) PS Lauda Jerusalem (147)
cap	Beata es Maria <i>ut supra</i> [not in E-E e-IV-10 or in the <i>Braga brev.</i>]
rubr	[E-E e-IV-10 only] <i>Capitulam in antea dicatur de dominica lectio [de] sancto si [e]venerit. [Braga brev.] Capitula hymnus et versiculo ut supra.</i>
H	Ave maris stella (008272) [not in E-E e-IV-10 or in the <i>Braga brev.</i>]
W	Elegit eam (008046.2) [not in E-E e-IV-10 or in the <i>Braga brev.</i>]
M	Ave gloriosa dei genitrix (200455.1) [E-E e-IV-10] Regina mundi et domina virgo (204242)
or	Concede nos famulos tuos quaesumus domine deus perpetua mentis et corporis sanitate gaudere et gloriosa beatae Mariae semper virginis intercessione a praesenti liberari tristitia et aeterna perfrui laetitia. Per dominum. [P-BRad Ms. 657] <i>oratio ut supra.</i> [E-E e-IV-10 and the <i>Braga brev.</i> lack the collect and have no other indication.]
rubr	[P-BRad Ms. 657 only] <i>Deinde dicantur commemorationes ut supra.</i> <i>Istae antiphonae supradictae et responsoria require in assumptione beatae virginis et in nativitate eiusdem in mensis augusti et septembris.</i>

Table 2. The nine-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum*.

Besides the four breviaries considered in the above Table 2, the nine-lesson Saturday office is also transmitted in further Braga sources: the mid-fifteenth-century breviary known as the ‘Duques de Palmela Breviary’, *P-BRs* s.s.;²² a Diurnal, datable to after 1455 and before 1467, *P-BRad* Ms. 1;²³ all printed breviaries after the 1494 *editio princeps*; and the antiphoners *P-BRs* Ms. 28 (c. 1510-15) and Ms. 17 (c. 1520), which contain only the chant pieces.

One of the distinctive characteristics of the three- and nine-lesson Braga offices is the choice of texts for the lessons at Matins. Instead of commentaries drawn from the Augustinian homiletic repertory, particularly pseudo-Augustinian sermons, which are frequently employed in Marian offices within the Cluniac lectionary tradition, especially for the Purification, Annunciation, Assumption, Nativity of Our Lady, and their octaves,²⁴ the three-lesson office uses the first book of Gregory of Elvira’s *Tractatus de Epithalamio*, the earliest surviving

²² See n. 21 above.

²³ See Rocha, *L’Office Divin*, pp. 51-2, n. 3.

²⁴ On the organisation of Cluniac Matins lectionaries and the use of homiletic readings, especially pseudo-Augustinian sermons, in Marian offices, see R. Étaix, ‘Le lectionnaire de l’office à Cluny’, *Recherches augustiniennes*, 10 (1976), pp. 91-159, Sanctoral, nos. 27-30, 42a-43, 125-127, 130, and 145-147.

commentary on the Song of Songs composed in Latin,²⁵ and so too does the nine-lesson office for the first two nocturns in all the breviaries, with the notable exception of the ‘Valasco Breviary’, *GB-Ob Ms. Lat. Liturg. e.12*, which, as seen in Table 2, gives the Song of Songs itself for the second nocturn.²⁶ According to Karl Shuve, Gregory of Elvira interprets the Song of Songs primarily in ecclesiological terms, identifying the bride and bridegroom as the Church and Christ, also allowing a Christological interpretation centred on the Incarnation.²⁷ However, this Christological dimension, at least in the first book of the *Epithalamium*, is not treated as subordinate. Rather, it is fully integrated into the ecclesiological reading and contributes equally to the interpretation of the biblical text.²⁸

For the third nocturn, the nine-lesson office adopts the homily of Bede, ‘Magnae devotionis et fidei’, on the lemma from Luke 11:27, ‘Extollens voce ... et ubera quae suxisti’, from the vigil of the feast of the Assumption.²⁹ Contrary to Gregory of Elvira’s commentary – which, to my knowledge, represents a unique choice – Bede’s homily is quite commonly used for different Marian feasts across Europe, including England and the Germanic area, particularly for the vigil of the Assumption, its original assignment in Braga. This same homily, ‘Magnae devotionis’, is also chosen for several other Iberian – particularly Aragonese and Catalan – Saturday Offices of Our Lady, for example in Zaragoza, Huesca–Jaca, and Lleida.³⁰

²⁵ Copied in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’, *P-BRad Ms. 657*, fols. 321^r-323^r, under the rubric ‘Incipit epithalamium [sic] Gregorii papae urbis Romae libri in cantica canticorum’. Critical edition of the complete work by E. Schulz-Flügel, *Gregorius Eliberritanus: Epithalamium sive Explanatio in Cantica Canticorum* (Fribourg, 1994). On the six extant sources of the *Epithalamium* (which do not include the ‘Soeiro Breviary’) and their issues of authorship attribution, see Schulz-Flügel, *Epithalamium*, pp. 99-116.

²⁶ This scribe-specific choice, although not uncommon, may be explained in this case by the character of the responsories in the second nocturn (*Virginis electae*, *Virginibus cunctis genitrix*, and *Hortus conclusus*), which exhibit a graded dependence on the Song of Songs. The eccentricities of the ‘Valasco Breviary’ and, particularly, the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’ (see nn. 12 above and 90 below), illustrating a certain plasticity of the Braga use, perhaps determined by their respective intended users, deserve proper study.

²⁷ K. Shuve, ‘Origen and the *Tractatus de Epithalamio* of Gregory of Elvira’, *Studia Patristica*, 50 (2011), pp. 189-203, at p. 189, acknowledges ‘a subordinate Christological dimension’ centred on the Incarnation.

²⁸ Gregory of Elvira, *Tractatus de Epithalamio* in the Schulz-Flügel edition (see n. 25), especially 1:2: ‘Hic autem Christi et Ecclesiae vox psallentis auditur, propter quod divina et humana sibimet invicem copulantur’ (‘Here, however, the voice of Christ and the Church singing is heard, through which the divine and the human are joined together with one another’), and 1:7: ‘Ecclesia enim, ut apostolus definivit, caro est Christi, qui ait: et ipse est caput corporis Ecclesiae’ (‘For the Church, as the Apostle defined it, is the flesh of Christ, who says: “and he himself is the head of the body, the Church”’), which emphasise the integration of ecclesiological and incarnational interpretation.

²⁹ Bede, *In Lucae Evangelio Expositio*, IV, PL 92:479-80. The ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’, *E-E e-IV-10*, gives the variant incipit ‘Maximae devotionis’. The text is variously attributed in the sources, as shown in Table 2.

³⁰ In the fourteenth-century breviary *E-E P-III-14* (Zaragoza), where the office is truncated after the third antiphon of Lauds, and in the printed breviaries of 1505 (Huesca–Jaca) and 1479 (Lleida), all of which have a nine-lesson office in which Bede’s homily, as usual, provides the lessons for the third nocturn.

Another distinguishing feature of the Braga offices is the series of Matins responsories.³¹ In the nine-lesson office, the first nocturn takes over the series used in the three-lesson office, consisting of two of the three responsories attributed to Fulbert of Chartres, *Stirps Jesse* (007709) and *Ad nutum domini* (006024), to which *Candida virginitas* (006262) is appended.³² Of the nine responsories, all except the fifth, *Virginibus cunctis genitrix* (602498.1), which appears nowhere else in the Braga use, correspond to items in the series of twelve responsories for the days within the octave of the Nativity of Our Lady in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’,³³ a series attested in part in the early twelfth-century antiphoner *E-Tc* Ms. 44.2, fol. 138^{r-v}. This antiphoner – of central importance in shaping most liturgical uses in north-western Iberia, as well as Toledo and the uses derived from it – contains only eight supplementary responsories; yet it includes *Virginibus cunctis* in the final position. The piece is also attested in the Saint-Martial of Limoges breviary *F-Pn* lat. 1254, fol. 154^v, as a late eleventh-century addition, consisting of only the text, double-spaced in order to leave room for the notation that was never written down.³⁴ No further witnesses of this responsory are

³¹ Corbin, *Essai*, pp. 350-61, discusses the responsories mostly individually, focusing on their early witnesses. She nevertheless notes that from the thirteenth century onwards, *Stirps Jesse*, *Ad nutum domini*, and *Candida virginitas* often appear at the end of nocturns in French and English breviaries, with few exceptions, most notably in Lescar – a suffragan diocese of Auch in Béarn with particular influence in Huesca – where, in its 1541 printed breviary, as in Braga, they are grouped in a single nocturn. She also mentions a pre-Humbertian Dominican composite manuscript first studied by Paul Cagin, who dates it to around 1232, with possible origin in Bologna, where the three responsories appear again together within the same nocturn under the rubric ‘In diebus sabbatorum quando celebratur officium beatae Mariae. Ad matutin. et in nativitate ejusdem isti tres Responsorii dicuntur. R. Ad nutum... V. Ut vitium... R. Candida virginitas. V. Que meruit... R. Stirps Jesse... V. Virgo dei genit. Gloria patri’; P. Cagin, ‘Un Manuscrit liturgique des Frères Prêcheurs antérieur aux Réglements d’Humbert de Romans’, *Revue des bibliothèques*, 9 (1899), pp. 163-200, quotation at p. 173. This manuscript is nowadays *DK-Kk* Ny Kongelig Samling 632 8^o, known as the ‘Copenhagen choirbook’, and more cautiously dated to after 1228 and before 1234; see P. Gleeson, ‘Dominican liturgical manuscripts from before 1254’, *Archivum Fratrum Praedicatorum*, 42 (1972), pp. 81-135, at pp. 93-9.

³² On the three Fulbert-attributed responsories, *Stirps Jesse*, *Ad nutum domini*, and *Solem justitiae* (007677) as a coherent messianic group celebrating Christ in his mother, see Corbin, *Essai*, p. 357. On the context of their creation and original performance, see M. Fassler, ‘Mary’s Nativity, Fulbert of Chartres, and the Stirps Jesse: Liturgical Innovation circa 1000 and Its Afterlife’, *Speculum*, 75/2 (2000), pp. 389-434, at pp. 416-22. The sequence in the Braga offices, which retains the first two responsories and replaces the third with *Candida virginitas*, introduces a more explicit Marian and intercessory emphasis, while preserving the underlying Christological and typological framework.

³³ *P-BRad* Ms. 657, fol. 263^f. This series appears in all later Braga breviaries.

³⁴ *F-Pn* lat. 1254 preserves the *lectio difficilior* of *Virginibus cunctis genitrix*, reading ‘qui mala sectando vinclis clastris capiamur iniquis’ at the end of the respond (the final letter of ‘clastris’ is blurred and cannot be identified with certainty, though in Carolingian script it would normally be a tall /s/; the form is, however, perfectly grammatical in this context). This reading is rhetorically fuller and metrically weightier than the progressively simplified forms found in *E-Tc* Ms. 44.2 and in later Portuguese sources. Other textual variants include ‘tu miserescere’ – ‘tu miserere’ in the printed breviaries and the Braga antiphoners; ‘tu misere’ in the ‘Soeiro’ and ‘Valasco’ breviaries and the Coimbra ‘Liber catenatus’ (*P-Cua* Cofre 27); ‘tui miserer’ in the ‘Fernão Duarte’ breviary. In ‘*Virginibus cunctis genitrix generosior adsis*’, ‘adsis’ is phonetically assimilated to ‘assis’ in some later sources. The forms ‘nostrum’ and ‘qui’ are preserved in *F-Pn* lat. 1254, whereas two later witnesses read ‘nostri’, and most read ‘cum’ or ‘dum’, respectively. In the remaining sources, ‘clastris’ is omitted, and in most cases ‘capiamur’ is regularised to ‘capimur’. The *lectio faciliior* occurs in the Portuguese manuscript tradition as ‘cum mala sectando vinclis capimur iniquis’, further normalised to ‘vinculis’ in the printed breviaries. These

attested until it reappears in Portugal in manuscript sources transmitting the nine-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum*.

In addition, the ninth responsory shows a minor variation, only apparently stabilised in the 1549 printed breviary.³⁵ In fact, despite the seeming difference and their separate identifiers on the *Cantus Index*, *Felix valde es, sacra virgo* (600873.1) and *Felix namque es, sacra virgo* (006725) are identical texts except for a single word: ‘valde’ is an adverb modifying the adjective ‘felix’ (‘You are greatly blessed, holy Virgin ... because from you arose the sun of justice’), whereas ‘namque’ is a conjunction introducing an explanation in the following clause (‘For indeed you are blessed, holy Virgin ... because from you arose the sun of justice’). In other words, the difference is purely one of discursive nuance, without affecting the semantic content, and the responsories are thus simply variants of one another, even sharing the same chant.

The nine-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum* is already transmitted, at least in its chant structure and repertory, in the Coimbra psalter-hymnal known as the ‘Liber catenatus’, most likely intended for use at Coimbra Cathedral and probably copied around 1350, under the rubric ‘In sollempni commemoratione beatae Virginis Mariae in sabbato’.³⁶ This witness predates the 1431 Braga synodal prescription and suggests that the nine-lesson form later adopted at Braga already circulated by the mid-fourteenth century. The lessons, chapters, and collects are not included in the ‘Liber catenatus’, but the chant pieces, except the hymns and the versicles, are notated in full. The seventh responsory, *Ave festiva* (600178), has a significant lacuna – the words ‘virgo o quam terribilis’ in the verse are omitted, although the music is distributed across the syllables of the remaining text – and the final responsory presents the variant ‘namque’, which, in Braga sources, first appears in printed breviaries, beginning with the 1494 impression.³⁷

The presence of the nine-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum* in the Coimbra ‘Liber catenatus’, several decades before its formal prescription at Braga in 1431, raises the question of how this

variations reflect a consistent pattern of simplification. As there is no evidence of interpolation in *F-Pn* lat. 1254, its reading most closely represents the archetypal form of the responsory text.

³⁵ The early sixteenth-century antiphoners of Braga continue to give *Felix valde* and *Felix namque* indifferently (*P-BRs* Ms. 17, fol. 144^{r-v} and fol. 174^r, respectively; *P-BRs* Ms. 28, fol. 286^{r-v} and fol. 290^{r-v}, respectively).

³⁶ *P-Cua* Cofre 27, fols. 181^r-188^v. The date of copying is determined by palaeographical criteria and by the fact that the book contains four hymns for the *Festo Victoriae Christianorum*, celebrating the victory of Portugal and Castile over the Emirate of Granada in the Battle of Rio Salado near Tarifa on 30 October 1340, which provides the *terminus post quem* for the manuscript. The ‘Liber catenatus’ offers evidence that elements later associated with Braga were already present in Coimbra by the mid-fourteenth century, notably in the Office of the Dead; see J. P. d’Alvarenga, ‘The Office of the Dead in Portuguese Medieval Uses’, *Portuguese Journal of Musicology*, new series, 4/1 (2017), pp. 167-204, at pp. 173, 179-81, and 183.

³⁷ See n. 35 above on the early sixteenth-century Braga antiphoners.

form relates to the Saturday Office of Our Lady referred to in the 1200 Coimbra charter of donation cited above. On the one hand, the relationship between the three- and nine-lesson forms remains difficult to define given the surviving evidence. The three-lesson office is attested only in Braga sources, whereas the nine-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum* is already attested in a Coimbra source of the mid-fourteenth century. On the other hand, a Coimbra attestation is compatible with the presence of the responsory *Virginibus cunctis genitrix*, since this piece, as noted, appears to have been known in late-eleventh-century Saint-Martial of Limoges, from which Coimbra received demonstrable influence.³⁸ However, this does not establish direct derivation, given the fragmentary nature of the surviving transmission. The version of Gregory of Elvira's *Epithalamium* as entered in the 'Soeiro Breviary', despite variations in wording and some corrupt readings, is sufficiently close to be placed under the same hyparchetype as that found in a collection of Biblical commentaries copied at Santa Cruz in Coimbra before the mid-twelfth century.³⁹ Still, this remains indicative rather than conclusive, given the complexities of the text's transmission.

There is, however, a hypothesis worth considering, though it cannot be verified at present due to the limited number of extant early sources, particularly from Coimbra. It may be inferred that a three-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum* was shared by Braga and Coimbra. In Coimbra, perhaps in the context of Pedro Salvado's donation of 1200, this office may have been expanded into the nine-lesson form later preserved in the 'Liber catenatus' around the middle of the fourteenth century. Braga, by contrast, would have continued to use the three-lesson office until 1431, when the synod convened by Archbishop Fernando da Guerra prescribed the celebration of nine lessons and thereby formalised within the Braga use a form of the office already attested in Coimbra. This is compatible with the formulation of the rubrics in the Braga breviaries, which merely state that 'statutum fuit ... quod ... fiant novem

³⁸ For instance, in the Office of the Dead, the series of Matins responsories in the 'Missale mixtum' of Coimbra Cathedral (*P-Cua* Cofre 42) likely derives from Saint-Martial; see Alvarenga, 'The Office of the Dead', p. 174. The connection with Saint-Martial of Limoges (which was donated to Cluny in 1062) is supported by the early career of Bishop Maurício, who was supposedly educated there and served as abbot of Saint-Pierre of Uzerche in the south Limousin (reformed by Saint-Martial in 1068, though not part of the Cluniac congregation), as well as archdean of Toledo Cathedral, before being elected Bishop of Coimbra in 1099 and then elected Archbishop of Braga between 1109 and 1118; see especially L. C. Amaral and F. Renzi, 'A medieval "enigma": About the ecclesiastical trajectory of the Archbishop of Braga and "Antipope" Gregory VIII, Maurice "Bourdin" (11th-12th centuries)', *Lusitania Sacra*, 48 (2023), pp. 87-122.

³⁹ *P-Pm* Ms. 800 (Santa Cruz 47), fols. 103^{ra}-128^{rb}, source 'P' in the Schulz-Flügel edition (see n. 25). This manuscript is here dated to the eleventh-twelfth century. In the *Catálogo dos Códices da Livraria de Mão do Mosteiro de Santa Cruz de Coimbra na Biblioteca Pública Municipal do Porto*, ed. A. A. Nascimento and J. F. Meirinhos (Porto, 1997), pp. 231-5, it is dated to the mid-twelfth century. However, the section in which the *Epithalamium* is copied employs transitional Visigothic script, which usually indicates a date before 1150.

lectiones' ('it was established ... that ... nine lessons be held') and do not necessarily imply the compilation of a new office.⁴⁰

The nine-lesson office is also included in an Augustinian breviary printed in 1514.⁴¹

According to its colophon, the book was ordered 'at the request of some priors' by Dionísio Gonçalves de Sequeira, abbot of the Church of Santa Eulália in Rio Covo near Barcelos, at his own expense, and arranged from a copy made at Santa Cruz in Coimbra for the Monastery of the Augustinian Canons Regular of São Simão da Junqueira near Vila do Conde, in the Archbishopric of Braga, which the commissioner 'corrected with the greatest diligence'.⁴²

The Augustinian Canons Regular of Santa Cruz did not have an independent Saturday Office of Our Lady. Instead, the Saturday commemoration formed part of the daily Hours of the Virgin, which are also preserved in the 1514 breviary,⁴³ through the use of proper alternative items. The inclusion of the *Cantica Canticorum* Office is explained by the fact that the monasteries for which this breviary was produced were located within the Archbishopric of Braga and were therefore subject to the obligation to celebrate it, in accordance with the provisions of the 1431 synod.

The exemplar for the Saturday Office of Our Lady in the Augustinian breviary appears to have been an intermediate source between the 'Fernão Duarte Breviary', probably copied in 1478 but whose content predates 1470, and the 1494 printed breviary of Braga.⁴⁴ Relative to the latter, the lessons are shorter, except for lesson 7, which matches it in length but retains the variant incipit 'Maximae devotionis' as in the 'Fernão Duarte Breviary'.⁴⁵ The office itself

⁴⁰ Although dependent on Braga, Coimbra retained a degree of independence in liturgical matters. One such example is the feast of the Conception, introduced in Coimbra in 1320 by Bishop Raymond d'Ébrard I and only five years later in Braga on the initiative of Canon João Escola, who in 1325 instituted a legacy for its annual celebration; see Rocha, *L'Office Divin*, pp. 192-3, n. 324. This provides a clear indication that some elements of the use of Braga, attested only in relatively late sources, may in fact have been adopted from its suffragan dioceses.

⁴¹ *Breviarium secundum ordinem diui augustini* (s.l. s.n., 1514) [*OSA brev.*], fols. 512^r-515^r.

⁴² [*OSA brev.*], fol. 523^{r-v}.

⁴³ [*OSA brev.*], fols. 77^r-80^r.

⁴⁴ The initial rubric is transcribed in Corbin, *Essai*, p. 366. It is similar to the rubrics found in the manuscript breviaries, except in matters of precedence rules and seasonal restrictions: '[...] in quolibet sabbato per totum annum [...] Exceptis festivitibus duplicibus et etiam festis quae habent iij. vi. et ix. Responsorium duplicatum et officium proprium. Et excepto tempore a passione domini usque ad pascha [...]' (throughout the whole year, except for double feasts, and also for feasts that have the third, sixth, and ninth responsories doubled and a proper office, and except for the period from the Lord's Passion [i.e. Passion Sunday] until Easter). It does not mention the 1470 synod convened by Archbishop Luís Pires, which excluded the Saturday office from being celebrated between the First Sunday in Advent and the Feast of the Purification, and between Passion Sunday and the Octave of Easter, as stated in the rubric of the 1494 printed breviary.

⁴⁵ Referring to the Schulz-Flügel edition of Gregory of Elvira's *Epithalamium* (see n. 25), the 1494 printed breviary of Braga gives, for lessons 1-6, paragraphs 1, 2, and 4-8 (to line 3) of the first book in the first recension – that is, the version that omits paragraphs 3 and 19 and presents shorter texts in paragraphs 16 and 27 – whereas the 1514 Augustinian breviary concludes lesson 6 with the final line of paragraph 6. The nine lessons supplied within the three-lesson office in the 'Fernão Duarte Breviary' (fols. 91^v-93^r), possibly intended either for

shows a number of particular features, among them the customary benedictions that precede each lesson at Matins, which are rarely written out in place;⁴⁶ the versicle for the third nocturn is *Speciosa facta es* (008202), as in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’ and the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’, while the 1494 printed breviary has *Specie tua et pulchritudine* (008201); and the Magnificat antiphon for Second Vespers is *Regina mundi et domina virgo* (204242), as in the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’, with the more common *Ave gloriosa dei genitrix* (200455.1) as the ‘other alternative antiphon’ (‘alia antiphona alternative’).

2. Évora

The Saturday Office of Our Lady was celebrated in Évora Cathedral before 1344 because, on 1 July of that year, the synod convened by Bishop Martinho Afonso ordered that in all the churches of the city and diocese ‘dicatur officium beatae Mariae semper Virginis cum novem lectionibus iuxta modum qui cantatur in ecclesia Elborensi’ (‘the Office of the Blessed Mary ever Virgin be said with nine lessons, according to the manner that is sung in the church of Évora’).⁴⁷ The breviary of Évora printed in 1528 presents a nine-lesson office under the rubric ‘Incipit officium beatae virginis mariae in sabbatis decantandum’,⁴⁸ which is outlined in Table 3 below.⁴⁹

alternation on successive Saturdays or for use in the nine-lesson office copied later on fols. 98^r-99^v, end with the last line of paragraph 7.

⁴⁶ The nine benedictions are:

- 1.1. Alma virgo virginum intercedat pro nobis ad suum filium.
- 1.2. Beatae Mariae intercessio fiat peccatorum nostrorum remissio.
- 1.3. Castitatem mentis et corporis tribuat nobis filius virginis.
- 2.1. Dele[at] nostra crimina qui natus es[t] de virgine Maria.
- 2.2. Eruat nos Jesus a peccatis per intercessionem suae matris.
- 2.3. Funde preces pia pro nobis virgo Maria.
- 3.1. Per evangelica dicta filius virginis nos benedicat.
- 3.2. Jesus Mariae filius sit nobis adjutor et propitius.
- 3.3. Qui natus es de virgine succurre nos quotidie.

This set closely parallels the benedictions in the 1549 breviary of Braga (see n. 11), fols. 94^v-96^r, except for the first, which ends ‘ad dominum’, and the seventh and ninth, which there read:

- 3.1. Per evangelium aeternum perducat nos rex in caelum.
- 3.3. Sancta dei genitrix sit nobis semper auxiliatrix.

The ‘horae beatae Mariae secundum vsum Elborensis ecclesiae fere per totum annum dicendae’ in the 1528 breviary of Évora, [*Évora brev.*], fols. 197^v-200^v, contains a similar series, except for the seventh benediction, which reads:

- 3.1. Ora mente pia pro nobis virgo Maria.

The ninth benediction in the Augustinian breviary corresponds to the eighth in the Évora breviary, whereas the ninth benediction in the 1549 Braga breviary occupies the same position in the Évora breviary.

⁴⁷ *Synodicon Hispanum, II: Portugal*, ed. A. García y García (Madrid, 1982), p. 205, canon 1: ‘De officio beate Marie diebus sabbatinis dicendo seu etiam recitando’.

⁴⁸ [*Évora brev.*], fols. 192^r-194^r. According to the *regulae generales*, the office was not celebrated during Advent and from Passion Sunday to the Octave of Corpus Christi, inclusive, and double feasts or feasts with a proper office (‘festum duplex [...] vel festum habens responsoria vel laudes’) took precedence over it; [*Évora brev.*], fol. [11]^v. The synod of 1344 (see n. 47 above) presents a different formulation: the Saturday Office was to be

Ad Vesperas	
cap	Sicut cinamomum et balsamum ... dedi suavitatem odoris. (Eccles. 24:20)
R	Hortus conclusus (601080)
H	Ave maris stella (008272)
W	Beatam me dicent omnes generationes R. Quia ancillam humilem respexit deus (800039)
M	Ave regina caelorum (001542.1)
or	Concede nos famulos ... [perfrui laetitia.]
Ad Completorium	
A	Dignare me laudare (002217)
cap	Tu autem [in nobis ... ne derelinquas nos domine deus noster.] (Jer. 14:9)
H	Te lucis (008399)
W	Custodi nos (008001)
N	Sub tuum praesidium (005041)
or	Visita quaesumus ... [et benedictio tua sit super nos semper.]
Ad Matutinum	
I	In honore beatissimae Mariae virginis jubilemus domino (001086) PS Venite (94)
H	Quem terra (008375)
In I noct.	
A1.1	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709) PS Domine dominus noster (8)
A1.2	Sicut myrrha electa (004942) PS Caeli enarrant (18)
A1.3	Haec est quae nescivit (003001) PS Domini est terra (23)
W	Diffusa est gratia (008014)
lect. 1	Sollemnem memoriam sacrosanctae virginis ... agonizanti in mortis periculo. (Poncelet, 1666)
R1.1	Ave festiva ferculi (600178)
V1	Monte Libano (600178a)
lect. 2	Denique dum illi exanimis ... vocatus ad titulum Mariae. (Ibid.)
R1.2	Hortus conclusus (601080)
V1	Fons hortorum puteus (601080a)
lect. 3	Beata itaque virgo Maria ... in heremi vastitate coronam. (Ibid.)
R1.3	Solem justitiae regem (007677)
V1	Cernere divinum lumen (007677a)
V2	Gloria (909000)
In II noct.	
A2.1	Specie tua et pulchritudine (004987) PS Eructavit (44)
A2.2	Dignare me laudare (002217) PS Deus noster refugium (45)
A2.3	Sicut laetantium (004936) PS Fundamenta (86)
W	Specie tua (008201)
lect. 4	Adducatur et alius miser ... facie filio suo reconciliavit. (Ibid.)
R2.1	Virga dedit florem (a00365)
V1	Gaudeat omnis homo (a00365a)
lect. 5	Et si haec preconia ... domine Mariae offerendum. (Ibid.)
R2.2	Stirps Jesse (007709)

celebrated from the Octave of Trinity Sunday until the First Sunday of Advent, and from the Octave of the Epiphany until Septuagesima, only double feasts taking precedence over it.

⁴⁹ Poncelet refers to A. Poncelet, 'Miraculorum B. V. Mariae quae saec. VI–XV latine conscripta sunt: Index postea perficiendus', *Analecta Bollandiana*, 21 (1902), pp. 241-360; Urfels-Capot refers to A.-E. Urfels-Capot, *Le Sanctoral du lectionnaire de l'office dominicain (1254–1256): Édition et étude d'après le ms. Rome, Sainte-Sabine XIV LI*, Mémoires et Documents de l'École des Chartes, 84 (Paris, 2007), online version at <<http://elec.enc.sorbonne.fr/sanctoral/>>.

V1	Virgo dei genitrix (007709a)
lect. 6	Salve inquam ave gloriosum ... salvet imperium pueri sui. (Ibid.)
R2.3	Stella maris fulget (a06932)
V1	Tua virgo prece (a06932a)
V2	Gloria (909000)
In III noct.	
A3.1	Gaude Maria virgo (002924) PS Cantate (95)
A3.2	In odorem unguentorum (003261) PS Dominus regnavit (96)
A3.3	Pulchra es et decora (004418) PS Cantate ii° (97)
W	Adjuvabit eam (007934)
lect. 7	<i>Secundum lucam</i> In illo tempore Loquente Jesu ad turbas: extollens vocem ... et ubera quae suxisti (Luke 11:27). Et reliqua. <i>Omelia venerabilis Bede presbyteri</i> Unigenitus dei charissimi aperte assumpta de intemerata virgine ... et ubera quae suxerat praedicavit. (Urfels-Capot, 97.7b)
R3.1	Post partum virgo (007400)
V1	Dei genitrix intercede (007400a)
lect. 8	At ille dixit: quinimmo beati qui audiunt verbum dei ... huius vite mortales custodivit. (Urfels-Capot, 97.8)
R3.2	Ora pro nobis (601702)
V1	Ut digni efficiamur (601702a)
lect. 9	O veneranda domina electa ... et virgo permansit in aeternum Maria. (Urfels-Capot, 97.8)
R3.3	Ad nutum domini (006024)
V1	Ut vitium virtus (006024a)
V2	Gloria (909000)
rubr	<i>Dicatur</i>
TD	Te deum laudamus (909010)
W	Ora pro nobis sancta dei genitrix R. Ut digni (800319)
In Laudibus	
A1	Post partum virgo (004332)
A2	Oculi tui sancta dei genitrix (004110)
A3	Maria virgo semper laetare (003708)
A4	Sub tuam protectionem (005040)
A5	Sub tuum praesidium (005041)
cap	Ego quasi vitis ... [fructus honoris et honestatis.] (Eccles. 24:23)
H	O gloriosa (008375e)
W	Elegit eam deus R. In tabernaculo (008046.2)
B	Gaude dei genitrix virgo (002920.1)
or	Deus qui de beatae Mariae ... [eius apud te intercessionibus adjuvemur.]
Ad Primam	
A	Hortus conclusus es (003137.1)
cap	Regi autem ... [honor et gloria in saecula saeculorum.] (1 Tim. 1:17)
R	Jesu Christi (601272)
V	Qui natus es (601272d)
or	In hac hora ... [in tuis laudibus iugiter delectemur.]
Ad Tertiam	
A	Sancta dei genitrix (004699.1)
cap	Et sic in Syon ... [in Jerusalem potestas mea.] (Eccles. 24:15)
R	Ora pro nobis (601702)
or	Deus qui salutis ... [auctorem vitae suscipe dominum nostrum.]
Ad Sextam	

A	In prole mater (003274)
cap	Et radicavi in populo ... [in plenitudine sanctorum detentio mea.] (Eccles. 24:16)
R	Sancta dei genitrix virgo (007568)
or	Deus qui virgi[nalem aulam ... facias suae interesse festivitati.]
Ad Nonam	
A	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)
cap	Quasi cedrus exaltata ... [quasi cypressus in monte Syon] (Eccles. 24:17)
R	Speciosa facta es (602225)
or	Famulorum tuorum ... [Jesu Christo intercessione salvemur.]
Ad II Vesperas	
rubr	<i>super psalmos</i>
A1	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709) PS Dixit dominus (109)
A2	Sicut myrrha electa (004942) PS Laudate pueri (112)
A3	Haec est quae nescivit (003001) PS Laetatus sum (121)
A4	In odorem unguentorum (003261) PS Nisi dominus (126)
A5	Pulchra es et decora (004418) PS Lauda Jerusalem (147)
rubr	<i>Capitulum Hymnus et versiculo ut in primis vespere</i>
M	Speciosa facta es (206209)
rubr	<i>Oratio ut supra. Completorium ut supra.</i>

Table 3. The nine-lesson Office in the 1528 Évora breviary.

In continuation, it gives an alternative series of lessons and responsories for Matins, with no indication as to their use:⁵⁰

Lect. 1-4

De puero hebreo quem beatam virgo illesum in fornace servavit.

Contigit quondam res tallis in civitate bituricensi ... in dei fide ferventes permanserunt. (Poncelet, 234)

Lect. 5-6

[De seculari qui ob devotum ave Mariae de inferno ereptus est.]

Erat quidam vir secularis rurali operi deditus ... quae cum eo in aeternum sit benedicta amen. (Poncelet, 480)

Lect. 7-9

Secundum Lucam

Exurgens Maria in diebus illis ... et salutavit Elizabeth (Luke 1:39-40). Et reliqua.

Omelia venerabilis Bede presbyteri.

Lectio quam modo audivimus sancti evangelii et redemptionis nostrae nobis semper veneranda ... quasi a se haec essent extulit. (Bede, *Homilia II. In Festo Visitationis Beatae Mariae*, PL 94:15)

R1.1 O quam pulchra es (a08503)

V Descendam in hortum meum (a08503a)

⁵⁰ [Évora brev.], fols. 194^r-195^v. Responsories whose Cantus IDs appear in *italics* are not attested in any other known source, with the exception of *O quam pulchra es*, *Cella redemptoris signo*, and *Ave porta Orientis*, which also occur in *P-Pm Ms. 368*. An edition of these texts is provided in Appendix 1. The sixth responsory in the main series, *Stella maris fulget* (a06932) – a short responsory which, together with its verse, takes the form of an accentual rhymed distich – appears in full only in the Évora and Braga breviaries (in the latter, it is the eighth in the series of twelve responsories for the days within the octave of the Nativity of Our Lady); the incipit recorded in the late fourteenth-century Zaragoza processional *B-BR IV/473* most likely refers to the responsory *Stella maris fulget cuncti gaudete fideles* (a08406), which is attested in other Aragonese and Catalan sources.

- R1.2 Cella redemptoris signo (*a08504*)
 V Virgo Maria stella David (*a08504a*)
 R1.3 Ave vulnerata charitate (*a08506*)
 V Sepulti resurrectio (*a08506a*)
 R2.1 Candida virginitas (006262)
 V Quae meruit dominum (006262a)
 R2.2 Ego dilecta languedo (*a08507*)
 V Filiae Jerusalem nuntiate (*a08507a*)
 R2.3 Ave porta Orientis (*a08508*)
 V Ante partum virgo manens (*a08508a*)
 R3.1 Stella maris miserans (*a08509*)
 V Frange cathenas mortis (*a08509a*)
 R3.2 Ave maria gratia plena (006155)
 V Benedicta tu inter mulieres (006155a)
 R3.3 Pulchrae sunt genae tuae (*a08510*)
 V Revertere revertere Sunamitis (*a08510a*)

Although there is no opening explanatory rubric, the First Vespers antiphon and psalmody were probably the same as in the pre-Advent daily Hours of the Virgin – here titled ‘horae beatae mariae secundum usum Elborensis ecclesiae fere per totum annum dicendae’ – namely the antiphon *Ave Maria gratia plena* (001539) and the ‘psalmi consueti’, that is, the Friday ferial cursus.⁵¹ Alternatively, they may have been taken from the feast prescribed for the day. The choice of texts for the lessons in the first and second nocturns, both in the main and the alternative series – three narratives of Marian miracles – suggests a relatively late date for the composition of this Office.⁵² The first six lessons of the main series use the first part of the legend known by the short title ‘Saturday’, which frames Saturday devotion to Mary through a full commemorative office and emphasises her miraculous intercessory power and favour towards the faithful. In the alternative series, the first four lessons use the complete ‘Jewish Boy: Jew of Bourges’, and the fifth and sixth lessons the entire ‘Landmark Removed’ (or ‘The Rustic Who Removed Landmarks’); these two tales form a complementary pair of exempla illustrating two aspects of Marian *miser cordia*: protection of the innocent and intercession for sinners.⁵³

⁵¹ [*Évora brev.*], fol. 200^r. Another possibility is the first antiphon of the ferial office, *In conspectu angelorum* (006893), with the same five psalms; [*Évora brev.*], fol. 52^r. Some breviaries of other uses whose Saturday Office also begins with the Vespers chapter are clear regarding the employment of the ferial office; see, for instance, the [*Toledo brev.*], fol. 184^v: ‘si feria vj dicitur officium feriale incipiendum est a capitulo beatae mariae’ (‘if the ferial office is said on Friday, it is to begin with the chapter of Blessed Mary’).

⁵² Likely after 1200, when the third bishop of Évora, Dom Paio – apparently an Augustinian canon regular and former cloistral prior at the Monastery of São Vicente de Fora in Lisbon – created the cathedral chapter on 24 April of that year. Narratives of miracles are also used as lessons elsewhere in other late Marian offices, such as the Conception, especially from the thirteenth century onwards; see S. Corbin, ‘Miracula beatae Mariae semper virginis’, *Cahiers de civilisation médiévale*, 10/39-40 (Juillet-décembre 1967), pp. 409-33.

⁵³ On the three narratives, see E. F. Wilson, *The Stella maris of John of Garland Edited, Together With a Study of Certain Collections of Mary Legends Made in Northern France in the Twelfth and Thirteenth Centuries* (Cambridge MA, 1946), pp. 207, 157-9, and 197-8, respectively.

‘Saturday’ is the last of a set of seventeen narratives labelled *TS* in the literature (from the titles of the first in the group, ‘Toledo’, and the last, ‘Saturday’), dated to the twelfth century, although it originated as a sermon, emerging in the mid-eleventh century before being incorporated into collections of miracles.⁵⁴ The two narratives in the alternative series belong to another group of seventeen labelled *HM* (that is, ‘Hildefonsus’–‘Murieldis’, the first and last legends in the set), dated to the eleventh century.⁵⁵ These narratives form part of the original core of Marian miracles and exempla that circulated throughout Europe in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries and were known in Portugal from at least the early decades after 1200, as attested by their inclusion in a *Mariale* once in the possession of the Cistercian Monastery of Alcobaça,⁵⁶ though likely not copied there.⁵⁷ The many variant readings show that the exemplars for the Alcobaça *Mariale* and the lessons in the Évora breviary belong to separate branches of the tradition, indicating that the texts enjoyed extensive dissemination through different routes of transmission.⁵⁸

⁵⁴ See H. Barré, ‘L’apport marial de l’Orient à l’Occident de saint Ambroise à saint Anselme’, *Études Mariales*, 19 (1962), pp. 27-89, at pp. 76-7, quotation at p. 77, where a number of early witnesses of ‘Saturday’, mostly French, are cited; see also Ihnat, *Mother of Mercy*, pp. 116-8.

⁵⁵ On the early collections of Marian miracles, see Wilson, *The Stella maris*, pp. 3-7.

⁵⁶ *P-Ln Alc.* 149, fols. 96^v-99^v (‘Saturday’), 38^v-39^v (‘Jewish Boy: Jew of Bourges’), and 32^{r-v} (‘Landmark Removed’). ‘Saturday’ is here presented as an actual sermon, as seen in the title ‘Sermo dulcissimus in quo et miraculum de sabbato beatae mariae dedicato’.

⁵⁷ On this manuscript, see especially A. A. Nascimento, ‘Um “Mariale” Alcobacense’, *Didaskalia*, 9 (1979), pp. 339-412; see also T. L. Amos, *The Fundo Alcobaça of the Biblioteca Nacional, Lisbon. Volume I: Manuscripts 1-150* (Collegeville MN, 1988), pp. 190-4, and *Inventário dos Códices Iluminados até 1500. Vol. 1: Distrito de Lisboa* (Lisbon, 1994), p. 133.

⁵⁸ This can be seen by comparing the opening sentence of ‘Saturday’ in both versions (words identical in both are given in **bold**; minimal punctuation has been added for clarity):

<i>P-Ln Alc.</i> 149, fol. 96 ^v	1528 Évora breviary, fol. 192 ^{r-v}
Sollemnem memoriam sanctae mariae matris domini decet filios ecclesiae sollemniter et officiosissimae celebrare, quippe cum multis sanctorum concessum fit quadam speciali dignitate familiaritatis, ut quicumque illorum celebres extiterint non fraudulentur salute ipsorum patrocini.	Sollemnem memoriam sacrosanctae virginis mariae matris domini decet filios ecclesiae solemnii officio celebrare, quippe cum multis sanctorum concessum fit quadam speciali dignitate familiaritatis, ut quicumque illorum celebres extiterint non fraudentur a salute ipsorum patrociniis.

The variants illustrate three main divergences between the two versions: expansion of the Marian title in the Évora breviary; rewriting of the phrase referring to the office celebration; and grammatical restructuring of the final clause (‘non fraudulentur ...’ / ‘non fraudentur ...’), showing that the changes are systematic and thus that the two texts reflect disjoint branches of transmission. By contrast, the version in the thirteenth-century French *passionale*, *B-Br Ms.* 98-100, fol. 148^{r-v}, is very close to that of Évora, likely standing in the same branch of transmission; see *Catalogus Codicum Hagiographicorum Bibliothecae Regiae Bruxellensis, Pars I: Codices Latini Membranei*, Tomus I (Brussels, 1886), p. 39. The same is true of the version preserved in the Bavarian early twelfth-century hagiographical miscellany *V-CVbav Reg.lat.498*, fols. 97^v-99^r. The version published in E. F. Dexter, *Miracula Sanctae Virginis Mariae* (Madison, 1927), pp. 48-51, from the twelfth-century (possibly Iberian) miscellany *US-Cu Philipps MS 25142* (which also includes ‘Jewish Boy: Jew of Bourges’ and ‘Landmark Removed’), represents yet another branch of the tradition.

The homily attributed to Bede, ‘Unigenitus dei’, chosen for the lessons of the third nocturn in the main series, also points to a relatively late date for this office.⁵⁹ Its first known attestation appears to be the pre-Humbertian Dominican breviary Santa Sabina XIV L2, probably copied in Paris, certainly before 1250, fols. 406^v-407^r, where it occurs in the vigil of the Assumption, with the same attribution and lesson distribution, but with corrupt readings.⁶⁰ It then entered the Dominican lectionary prototype of Humbert of Romans included in Santa Sabina XIV L1 (copied in Paris between 1256 and 1259), fols. 142^r-230^v, with the same liturgical assignment, though in a longer form, with correct readings (suggesting the use of a different exemplar, since it is marked as having been taken from the source by selection, and not rewritten), and a different arrangement of lessons. Outside the Dominican tradition,⁶¹ and apart from Évora, the text is found in a thirteenth-century lectionary of Beaune, in central Burgundy, similarly assigned to the vigil of the Assumption and attributed to Bede, though with a different division into lessons,⁶² and in the printed breviaries of Riga in Latvia (here assigned to the Saturday Office of Our Lady)⁶³ and Nidaros (Trondheim) in Norway.⁶⁴ The text length and lesson distribution found in the Évora breviary seem to appear only in the pre-Humbertian Dominican breviary, in the 1519 printed breviary of Nidaros and in Dominican breviary incunabula.⁶⁵ However, as the variants in wording and the omissions suggest, the Évora

⁵⁹ In the alternative series, Bede’s homily ‘Lectio quam (modo) audivimus sancti evangelii’, chosen for the third nocturn, is taken from Friday in the third week of Advent, its most common assignment, which goes back to the Carolingian homiliary of Paul the Deacon; see R. Grégoire, *Les homéliaires du moyen âge: inventaire et analyse des manuscrits*, *Rerum Ecclesiasticarum Documenta, Series Maior, Fontes*, 6 (Rome, 1966), p. 78. The same text is found in the third nocturn in the Compostela Saturday Office of Our Lady; see *Breviarium Compostellanum* (Lisbon: Nicolau de Saxónia, 1497), fol. Kijj^v. This 1497 office of Compostela was, however, also compiled at a relatively late date, since it uses as lessons in the first and second nocturns the *Liber de laudibus beatae Mariae Virginis*, generally, though not securely, attributed to Vincent of Beauvais, but originating in a thirteenth-century Dominican milieu.

⁶⁰ For example, the opening clause reads ‘Unigenitus dei carissimi ante assumptam de intemerata virgine nostrae mortalitatis suffocata’, where the last word is a clear, and hardly intelligible, corruption of ‘substantiam’, resulting in semantic collapse.

⁶¹ A tradition that includes the Teutonic Order, which adopted the Dominican liturgy in 1244; see A. Potthast, *Regesta pontificum romanorum inde ab a. post Christum natum MCXCVIII ad a. MCCCIV*, vol. 2 (Berlin, 1875), p. 958, no. 11257.

⁶² Urfels-Capot, *Le Sanctoral*, note b to no. 97.7b, notes the presence of this pseudo-Bede homily in *F-BEA* Ms. 8, *Lectionarium ad usum beate Marie Belnensis Ecclesie*, fol. 191^{r-v}, dating the folios containing it to the twelfth century. The homily, without attribution, is also included in *D-DÜI* Ms. C 17, a composite volume dated 1467 and produced at the female Cistercian monastery of Kentrup in the Diocese of Cologne; see *Kurzinventar der Handschriften der Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Düsseldorf*, available through *Manuscripta Mediaevalia Handschriftenkataloge*, <<https://bilder.manuscripta-mediaevalia.de/hs/kataloge-online.htm>>.

⁶³ *Breviarium secundum ritum et usum sancte rigensis ecclesie* (Paris: Wilhelm Corver, 1513), beginning at fol. 127^r; ed. in H. von Bruiningk, *Messe und kanonisches Stundengebet nach dem Brauche der Rigaschen Kirche im späteren Mittelalter* (Riga, 1904), pp. 230-7, lessons 7-9 at pp. 234-5.

⁶⁴ *Breviaria ad usum ritumque sacrosanctem Nidrosiensis ecclesiae* (Paris: Jean Kerbriant and Jean Bienayse, 1519), fols. 383^v-384^r; modern edition as *Breviarium Nidrosiensis*, ed. I. Sperber, with an introduction by E. Karlsen and S. Hareide (Oslo, 2019), available at <bokselskap.no/boker/breviarium>.

⁶⁵ See, for instance, *Breviarium secundum ordinem sancti Dominici* (Venice: Johann von Köln and Nicholas Jenson, 1481), fol. [265]^r; *Breviarium secundum fratrum ordinem predicatorum* (Venice: Nikolaus von

breviary reflects possible local adaptation, including some grammatical simplification but preserving the core theological content, with an intensified Marian focus, and no direct dependence on a Dominican exemplar can be securely established.⁶⁶

The main series of responsories is anchored on *Ave festiva ferculi* – a theological synthesis of Mary as the dwelling of divine presence and example of charity expressed through her interior martyrdom – opening the first nocturn, and on the three Fulbert-attributed texts in the order in which they appear in *F-Pn* lat. 14167:⁶⁷ *Solem justitiae* (007677, here closing the first nocturn), *Stirps Jesse* (in the middle position of the second nocturn), and *Ad nutum domini* (closing the third nocturn). The responsories attributed to Fulbert are essentially Christological in nature, presenting Christ through Marian typology in the dawning of the Sun of Justice (*Solem justitiae*), Davidic lineage (*Stirps Jesse*), and divine volition governing paradoxical generation (*Ad nutum domini*). The other responsories – notably *Hortus conclusus* (601080) and *Virga dedit florem* (a00365) – form an amplificatory layer of Marian typology, drawing on Song of Songs imagery and Incarnation motifs. This is followed by an intercessory layer of shorter formulaic texts, including *Stella maris fulget* (a06932), *Post partum virgo* (007400), and *Ora pro nobis* (601702), marking a shift from dense typological exposition to devotional invocation and supplication.

The first five responsories are taken from the series for the days within the octave of the Assumption (whereas in Braga, as noted above, all the responsories, except *Virginibus cunctis*, come from the corresponding series for the Nativity of Our Lady); *Stella maris fulget* and *Ad nutum domini* do not appear elsewhere in the Évora breviary.

Frankfurt, 1488), fol. 287^{r-v}; *Breviarium ordinis predicatorum sancti Dominici* (Basel: Jakob Wolff, 1492), fol. 106^r (black numbering).

⁶⁶ For example, in the Dominican prototype and later manuscript lectionaries (as well as in the breviary of Riga), the opening clause reads:

‘Unigenitus dei filius fratres carissimi dominus noster Jesus Christus ante assumptam de intemerata virgine nostrae mortalitatis substantiam’.

The printed Dominican breviaries and the Nidaros breviary give a shorter reading, omitting ‘filius fratres’ and ‘dominus noster Jesus Christus’:

‘Unigenitus dei carissimi ante assumptam de intemerata virgine nostrae mortalitatis substantiam’.

The Évora breviary gives the reading:

‘Unigenitus dei carissimi aperte assumpta de intemerata virgine nostrae mortalitatis substantia’.

These differences – the reformulation of ‘ante assumptam’ as ‘aperte assumpta’ and the change from ‘substantiam’ to ‘substantia’ – illustrate the type of variation that may reflect local adaptation, involving simplification (including grammatical and textual reduction) in the course of the text’s transmission. Its diffuse yet sparse circulation and fluid attribution are illustrated by a fragment of a fourteenth-century German notated breviary, *D-Shsta* A 572 Bū 37b, which preserves the first lesson, ‘Unigenitus dei ... quae suxerat praedicavit’, in its shorter reading, immediately followed by the opening of Bede’s homily, ‘Magnae devotionis ... negando Mariam semper virginem’, and attributes the entire sequence to ‘beati Augustini episcopi’; see <<https://fragmentarium.ms/overview/F-htm>>.

⁶⁷ A mid-eleventh-century collection of the letters and homilies of Fulbert, bishop of Chartres, originally part of the library of the Abbey of Saint-Père-en-Vallée in Chartres. The texts of the responsories are copied on fol. 52^r.

The alternative series of responsories is largely composed of pieces so far unattested elsewhere, with only *Candida virginitas* in the fourth position and *Ave Maria gratia plena* (006155) in the eighth position. The former responsory is taken from Matins of the Assumption, while the latter, like *Post partum virgo* in the main series, is used in different Marian feasts. Of the remaining responsories, three – *O quam pulchra es* (a08503), *Cella redemptoris signo* (a08504), and *Ave porta Orientis* (a08508) – also appear in *P-Pm Ms. 368*.⁶⁸ These responsories are only loosely unified, as they draw on a shared Marian–Christological vocabulary derived mainly from the Song of Songs, Luke, and broader Marian typologies. As can be seen in Appendix 1, they do not display consistent formal or compositional coherence, but vary considerably in rhetorical density, structure, and degree of paraphrastic expansion, which may suggest compilation from different sources, as yet untraced.

In the 1548 edition of the Évora breviary, prepared by the Dominican friar and humanist André de Resende – the last before the cathedral chapter accepted the reformed Roman Breviary of Pius V on 22 December 1570⁶⁹ – the Saturday office underwent substantial reworking, marked by a theological reconfiguration. An additional Magnificat antiphon was supplied for First Vespers; the lessons of Matins were replaced; the corresponding series of responsories was changed; and complementary seasonal cursus were newly compiled (Advent season; from the Octave of the Epiphany to the Purification; from the Octave of Easter to the Ascension).⁷⁰

3. *P-Pm Ms. 368*

Once part of the library of the Monastery of Santa Cruz in Coimbra, *P-Pm Ms. 368* is a temporal breviary of the canons' cursus, which Corbin says is 'postérieur à 1317, car il contient l'office de saint Louis de Toulouse; il faut sans doute le placer vers le milieu du XIV^e siècle. Il a appartenu à un monastère de Chanoines réguliers du diocèse de Braga; on y trouve

⁶⁸ See n. 50 above.

⁶⁹ *P-EVc CEC 13-III, Livro 1.º das Lembranças do Cabido que começou em 1569 até 1574*, fol. 31^r.

⁷⁰ *Breviarium Eborensis* (Lisbon: Luís Rodrigues, 1548), cols. 738-65. The extra Magnificat antiphon is *Alma redemptoris mater*, given in the first position. The Matins lessons are taken from Pseudo-Augustine, *Sermo CXCIV De Annuntiatione Dominica*, III (PL 39:2107-10), in the first and second nocturns, and from Bede, *In Lucae Evangelium Expositio*, IV (PL 92:479-80), in the third nocturn. The revised responsories draw on both the original main and alternative series: 1.1 *Ave festiva ferculi*; 1.2 *Hortus conclusus*; 1.3 *Stirps Jesse*; 2.1 *Post partum virgo*; 2.2 *O quam pulchra es*; 2.3 *Ad nutum domini*; 3.1 *Ave Maria gratia plena*; 3.2 *Una est columba mea*; 3.3 *Candida virginitas*. The eighth responsory, *Una est columba mea* (a08612), together with its verse, 'Viderunt eam filiae Syon' (a08612a) – a near-quotation of Cant. 6:8 with selective omissions – is likely the result of the juxtaposition of two antiphons, the second being 005395.

en effet les fêtes de saint Gérald et de sainte Senhorinha'.⁷¹ In fact, its *terminus post quem* must be placed in 1323, because St Thomas Aquinas – ‘Sancti thome de ordine predicatorum’ – canonised in that year, is included among the suffrages of the saints,⁷² or even in 1334, because of the presence of the Feast of Trinity Sunday and the numbering of the summer Sundays by reference to it. A copying date in the mid-fourteenth century is, therefore, plausible, also considering palaeographical and codicological criteria.⁷³ However, its origin or use in a monastery of canons regular in the Diocese of Braga is highly unlikely.

St Senhorinha (c. 924-982), a nun who lived in the historic region of Terras de Basto, to the east of Braga and, according to the hagiographic tradition, a relative of the Bishop of Dume, St Rosendo of Celanova, was canonised in 1130 by the authority of Paio Mendes, Archbishop of Braga, and was the object of local devotion and peregrination during the late Middle Ages.⁷⁴ She appears in Augustinian Canons Regular calendars (first as an addition in *P-Pm* Ms. 843, a composite liturgical manuscript from Santa Cruz in Coimbra with components dating to the late twelfth and the late thirteenth century⁷⁵), but is absent from the calendar of Coimbra Cathedral⁷⁶ and only officially entered the breviary of Braga in 1724.⁷⁷ Apparently, she was not celebrated to the south of the Tagus River, since she is not named in the Évora breviary.⁷⁸ The presence of St Senhorinha is therefore consistent with a Coimbra milieu and does not support an origin or use of the breviary in the Diocese of Braga. Furthermore, the

⁷¹ Corbin, *Essai*, p. 363. In the *Catálogo dos códices*, pp. 289-90, the manuscript is wrongly described as a ‘Calendar, Missal, Breviary (old rite)’ with ‘Origin: Santa Cruz’. Its contents are as follows:

1 ^r -6 ^v	Calendar
7 ^r -82 ^r	Psalter with hymns, ending with the <i>Te Deum</i> , Gloria, Nicene Creed, Apostles’ Creed, <i>Pater noster</i> , and <i>Ave Maria</i> (incomplete: starts with Ps. 3)
82 ^r -85 ^r	Office of the Dead
85 ^r -88 ^v	Penitential Psalms
88 ^v -90 ^v	Litany
90 ^v -98 ^r	Little Office of the Blessed Virgin Mary
98 ^r -104 ^v	Saturday Office of the Blessed Virgin Mary
104 ^v -106 ^v	‘St Augustine’s Prayer’ (Alcuin, <i>De usu psalmodum</i> , I, 6, PL 101:476D-479A)
107 ^r -116 ^r	Suffrages of the Saints
117 ^r -348 ^v	Temporale (Dom. 1 Adventus to Dom. 25 p. Trinitatis, with important lacunae)

⁷² *P-Pm* Ms. 368, fol. 108^v.

⁷³ The manuscript shows a consistent preference for orthographic variants such as ‘set’ for ‘sed’ and ‘ac’ for ‘et’, a usage not commonly attested, to my knowledge, in Portuguese liturgical manuscripts of this period. This may reflect scribal habit or exemplar influence.

⁷⁴ See *Hagiografia e História: Banco de dados das hagiografias ibéricas (séculos XI ao XIII)*, coordinated by A. C. L. F. Silva (Rio de Janeiro, 2009), p. 18; G. J. A. C. Dias, ‘D. Sancho I, peregrino e devoto de Santa Senhorinha de Basto’, *Revista da Faculdade de Letras: História*, 13 (1996), pp. 63-70, at p. 65.

⁷⁵ *P-Pm* Ms. 843, fol. 183^r; [*OSA brev.*], fol. 3^r; *Breviarium secundum usum insignis monasterii sanctem crucis colibriensis ordinis diui augustini* (Coimbra: German Galhard, 1531), fol. [iiii]^v.

⁷⁶ See *Manuale secundum consuetudinem alme Colymbriensis ecclesie* (Lisbon: Nicolau Gazini, 1518), fol. [ii]^r.

⁷⁷ *Breviarium Bracharense ab Illustrissimo Domino D. Rudericco de Moura Telles Archipraesule, ac Domino Bracharae Hispaniorum Primate, reformatum, auctum, & recognitum. Pars Hyemalis* (Braga, 1724).

⁷⁸ See [*Évora brev.*], fol. [4]^v.

presence of saints originating from the Braga region in its calendar, apart from Senhorinha, is limited to Gerald. By contrast, saints associated with the Tagus valley region are present – Verissimus, Maximus, and Julia of Lisbon and Irene (Iria) of Santarém – alongside Iberian saints of limited but wider diffusion, among whom Vincent, Sabina, and Christeta of Ávila are given on 28 October, as in other Iberian calendars; Braga, by contrast, places the feast on the previous day, 27 October.⁷⁹ The ‘Officium pro fratribus et benefactoribus defunctis’ on 28 September finds parallels in Franciscan calendars⁸⁰ but does not necessarily point to a Franciscan background, which is contradicted by the liturgical content of the manuscript. The series of responsories for the Triduum is the same as that found in Braga and in Évora, with some significant differences.⁸¹ The first responsory of Maundy Thursday, *In monte Oliveti* (006916), has the variant reading ‘In montem Oliveti oravit Jesus ad patrem’. The form ‘montem’ appears in early French sources, such as the antiphoner of Mont-Renaud and the antiphoner of Compiègne, and also in Toledo 44.1 (*E-Tc* Ms. 44.1). The explicit-subject interpolation ‘Jesus’ can be found in a number of central Italian Franciscan sources, in Beneventan sources, in a few Catalan sources,⁸² in the Toledo breviary,⁸³ and in the antiphoner of Marseille (*F-Pn* lat. 1090).

On Good Friday, the first responsory, *Omnes amici mei* (007313), comes with the verse ‘Inter iniquos projecerunt me’ (007313zc), as in Toledo 44.1, Arles-sur-Tech, Compostela, Orense, Huesca, and the Franciscans,⁸⁴ instead of the more common ‘Et dederunt in escam’ (007313a), as in Braga and in Évora; the verse of the sixth responsory, *Barabbas latro* (006159), is a hitherto unattested variant of ‘Ecce turba’ (006159a) that reads ‘Ecce turba et mercator Judas venit et dum appropinquaret ad eum’;⁸⁵ and the ninth responsory is a metaphorical rephrasing of *Animam meam dilectam* (006101), reading ‘Vineam meam electam tradidi in manus impiorum’ instead of ‘Animam meam dilectam tradidi in manus

⁷⁹ See Rocha, *L’Office Divin*, p. 84.

⁸⁰ H. Grotefend, *Taschenbuch der Zeitrechnung des deutschen Mittelalters und der Neuzeit*, 13th ed. (Hannover, 1991), HTML version by H. Ruth, at <https://www.handschriftenzentren.de/materialien/grotefend/kalender/orden_12.htm>

⁸¹ For a comparison and analysis of the responsorial for Advent and the Triduum in selected Cluniac (notably the breviary of Saint-Pierre in Moissac, *F-Pic* lat. 1, and the ‘Aquitanian antiphoner’, *E-Tc* Ms. 44.2) and Iberian sources, see Rocha, *L’Office Divin*, pp. 381-441.

⁸² See <<https://cantusindex.org/id/006916>>.

⁸³ [*Toledo brev.*], fol. 94^v.

⁸⁴ This list of uses and sources is not fully comprehensive; see <<https://cantusindex.org/id/007313zc>>.

⁸⁵ The common reading of this verse is ‘Ecce turba et qui vocabatur Judas venit et dum appropinquaret ad Jesum’.

iniquorum’, and at the close of the respond has ‘qui me cognosceret et faceret bene’ in place of ‘qui me agnosceret et faceret bene’.⁸⁶

Finally, the sixth responsory of Holy Saturday, *Ecce quomodo moritur* (006605), has the verse ‘Tamquam agnus coram tondente’ (006605b), as in Toledo 44.1, Compostela, Orense, Huesca, and the Franciscans,⁸⁷ instead of the rare ‘In pace in idipsum’ (006605zb), found only in Toledo 44.2 (*E-Tc* Ms. 44.2), Braga, Évora, and Salamanca.

The series of responsories and their verses for Matins of the Office of the Dead is the same as in Évora, with two extra responsories: *Ne recorderis* (007209), with the verse ‘Dirige domine’ (007209a), and *Libera me domine de viis* (007092), with the verse ‘Clamantes et dicentes’ (007092a). The former, with the same verse, is the sixth responsory in Braga, Coimbra Cathedral, and the Roman-Franciscan series, and is one of the most frequently specified in the institution of anniversaries;⁸⁸ the latter is the ninth in the Roman-Franciscan series, often alternating with *Libera me domine de morte* (007091). The Magnificat antiphon is *Omne quod dat mihi pater* (004115), as in the use of Santa Cruz in Coimbra, while Braga, Évora, and Coimbra Cathedral have *Audivi vocem de caelo* (001528). The series of Lauds antiphons is also the same as in Santa Cruz, with *A porta inferi erue* (001191) in the fourth position, where Braga, Évora, and Coimbra Cathedral have *Eruisti domine* (002674).⁸⁹ Lastly, the Benedictus antiphon is *Ego sum resurrectio* (002601) – the only one in Évora, Coimbra Cathedral (in the ‘Missale mixtum’), and the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’, and the alternative antiphon in all Braga sources except the ‘Soeiro Breviary’ and the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’ – alongside the alternative *Absolve domine animas eorum* (001211), which is the only one in Santa Cruz,

⁸⁶ ‘impiorum’ and ‘cognosceret’ are the readings of the corresponding Old Hispanic responsory (h02024) in the tenth-century antiphoner of León (*E-L* Ms. 8), although the two texts read differently at other points.

⁸⁷ The same observation applies as in n. 84 above; see <<https://cantusindex.org/id/006605b>>.

⁸⁸ For example, Lourenço Vicente, Archbishop of Braga, who died in 1397, entrusted the canons of the cathedral with ‘huum universairo em que diguam [...] respomso de *Ne recorderis* ou de *Libera me Domine* e oraçam *Deus qui inter apostolicos*, *Deus qui nos patres et matres* e *Inclina Domine aurem tuam*’ (‘an anniversary in which they say [...] the responsory *Ne recorderis* or *Libera me Domine* and the prayers *Deus qui inter apostolicos*, *Deus qui nos patres et matres*, and *Inclina Domine aurem tuam*’); *P-Brad* Colecção Cronológica, caixa 24, doc. 910, quoted from A. M. S. A. Rodrigues, ‘A comemoração dos defuntos nos finais da Idade Média’, in *A Catedral de Braga: Arte, Liturgia e Música dos fins do século XI à época tridentina*, ed. A. M. S. A. Rodrigues and M. P. Ferreira (Lisbon, 2009), pp. 136-47, at p. 140.

⁸⁹ The same series of Lauds antiphons with *A porta inferi* in the fourth position followed by the Benedictus antiphon *Ego sum resurrectio* can be found in the fragment of a fifteenth-century notated breviary, *P-Cua* IV-3^a Gav. 44 (07), whose remaining content – items for the Presentation of Mary – ‘seems to correspond to the use of Coimbra Cathedral, replicated in Évora’, according to the *Portuguese Early Music Database* (PEM), at <<https://pemdatabase.eu/source/96919>>. However, the feast of the Presentation is absent from the Évora breviary and the square black notation of French derivation on a four-line stave strongly indicates an origin beyond the Pyrenees.

while Braga and Coimbra Cathedral (in the ‘Liber catenatus’) have *Omne quod dat mihi pater* (004115).⁹⁰

Besides the Triduum and the Office of the Dead, the responsorial of Advent is also useful for identifying liturgical lineages. Because of its many lacunae, only the First Sunday and the following weekdays of the Advent series in *P-Pm* Ms. 368 can be considered. The Sunday series is the same as in Braga and Évora. The Monday series is the same as in Braga, the difference with Évora being the versicle attached to the second responsory, *Obsecro domine* (007305) – ‘A solis ortu’ (007305a) in the former and *P-Pm* Ms. 368, ‘Qui regis Israel’ (007305b) in the latter – and the third responsory, which in Braga and *P-Pm* Ms. 368 is *Laetentur caeli* (007068) with the verse ‘Orietur in diebus’ (007068b), and in Évora is *Montes Israel* (007177) with the verse ‘Florete flores’ (007177zb). For Tuesday, Braga and Évora have no proper responsories. *P-Pm* Ms. 368 gives *Montes Israel* with the verse ‘Rorate caeli’ (007177a), *Erumpant montes* (006672) with the verse ‘De Syon exhibit’ (006672za), and *Aspiciebam in visu* (006128), which is repeated from the Sunday series, where it occupies the second position, with the verse ‘Potestas eius’ (006128b). This corresponds to the Franciscan series for Tuesday after the First Sunday in Advent.

The daily Hours of the Virgin for the period between the Feast of the Purification and the end of the Summer season – ‘horae dicendae in cotidiana commemoratione beatae mariae virginis a festo purificationis usque ad adventum domini’ – correspond exactly, except for the memorials, the Vespers versicle, and the Magnificat antiphon, to the ‘horae beatae mariae secundum vsum Elborensis ecclesiae fere per totum annum dicendae’ in the 1528 Évora breviary, including the lessons, chapters and collects, and the remaining chant pieces.⁹¹

Finally, the name ‘Alfonso’ appears inserted in a long prayer taken from Alcuin’s *De usu psalmodum*, here titled ‘oratio sancti augustini’, in the form ‘ut avertas iram tuam a me famulo

⁹⁰ As noted above (in n. 12), the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’ also presents a similarly eclectic Office of the Dead: the series of Matins responsories and their verses is the same as in Évora (except the extra responsories); the Magnificat antiphon, *Audivi vocem de caelo*, and the series of Lauds antiphons are the same as in Braga, Évora, and Coimbra (with *Eruisti domine* in the fourth position); and the Benedictus antiphon is *Ego sum resurrectio* (the only antiphon in Évora and the Coimbra ‘Missale mixtum’, the first antiphon in *P-Pm* Ms. 368, and the alternative antiphon in the other Braga sources except the ‘Soeiro Breviary’). On the Office of the Dead, see Alvarenga, ‘The Office of the Dead’ (see n. 36).

⁹¹ *P-Pm* Ms. 368, fols. 90^v-94^v; [*Évora brev.*], fols. 197^v-200^v. Memorials for the Holy Cross, Peter and Paul Apostles, St James, St Vincent, All Saints, and for Peace in Évora; All Saints and for Peace in *P-Pm* Ms. 368. At the Magnificat, Évora gives the antiphon *Virgo Maria non est tibi similis ... sancta dei genitrix* (005453.1); the breviary *P-Pm* Ms. 368 gives, in this order, *Sancta Maria succurre miseris ... pro devoto femineo sexu* (004703.1), *Sancta Maria virginum piissima* (204390), and *Beata dei genitrix Maria virgo perpetua ... pro devoto femineo sexu* (001563), as alternative antiphons.

tuo alfonso’,⁹² suggesting that the text was adapted for the devotional use of an individual cleric, most likely the owner or recipient of the manuscript rather than its scribe.

In conclusion, in light of both its liturgical evidence and traces of individual devotional adaptation, *P-Pm* Ms. 368 is best understood as a mid-fourteenth-century breviary copied in a Coimbra-centred context. It incorporates elements from the use of Santa Cruz also reflecting the reception of the use of Coimbra Cathedral – often mirrored in Évora – even if that use was not stable,⁹³ and the selective incorporation of Braga (where these differ from Évora), Franciscan, and broader Iberian liturgical traditions, especially those associated with Auch, which reached Huesca through its suffragan dioceses in Béarn, and Compostela and Orense through the influence of Toledo 44.1, or sources derived from it.⁹⁴ In the absence of evidence for cathedral or regular use, a local collegiate church setting cannot be excluded.

The Saturday Office of Our Lady presented in this breviary under the rubric ‘In solemnī commemoratione beatae virginis mariae quae fit in sabbatis’ is outlined in Table 4 below.⁹⁵

Ad Vesperas	
cap	Sicut cinamomum et balsamum ... dedi suavitatem odoris. (Eccles. 24:20)
R	Candida virginitas (006262)
V	Quae meruit dominum (006262a)
H	Ave maris stella (008272)
W	Beatam me dicent omnes generationes R. Quia fecit (a08645)
1M	Alma redemptoris mater (001356)
2M	Mater patris et filia (205362)
rubr	<i>alia antiphona</i>
3M	Speciosa facta es (206209)
or	Concede nos famulos tuos

⁹² *P-Pm* Ms. 368, fols. 104^v-106^v, at fol. 105^v. The more common reading in the *De usu psalmodum* tradition is ‘ut avertas iram tuam a famulo tuo’, without any personal name. The addition of ‘Alfonso’ should thus be understood as a manuscript-specific interpolation. This prayer, ‘Domine Jesu Christe qui in hunc mundum propter nos peccatores ... indulgeat mihi dominus omnia peccata mea hic et in futuro saeculo amen’, with variations in wording and commonly attributed to St Augustine, frequently appears in fourteenth- and fifteenth-century books of hours and collections of prayers (for example, in *F-Pn* lat. 1072, fols. 159^v-164^r, and *F-Pn* lat. 10527, fols. 99^v-109^v), and is also found in vernacular translation (as, for example, in *GB-Lbl* Add MS 43683, fols. 22^v-33^r, where it occurs in an Italian version). Its inclusion in breviaries appears to be unusual.

⁹³ As noted by M. P. Ferreira, ‘Fragments and Places: Establishing Connections’, in *Fragmenta Musicae: Contemporary Perspectives*, ed. J. P. d’Alvarenga, M. P. Ferreira, and A. M. Seïça, Épitome musical (Turnhout, 2025), pp. 69-80, at pp. 79-80.

⁹⁴ Toledo 44.1 is related to Toulouse and, particularly, to the Abbey of Saint-Orens in Auch, where it would have been copied. On the ancestry of the use of Huesca and the influence of Toledo 44.1 in Compostela and Orense, see J. P. Rubio Sadia, ‘La introducción del Rito Romano en la Iglesia de Toledo. El papel de las Órdenes religiosas a través de las fuentes litúrgicas’, *Toletana*, 10 (2004), pp. 151-77, at pp. 167-8 and 175-6; and D. Saulnier, ‘Des variantes musicales dans la tradition manuscrite des antiennes du répertoire romano-franc: Description, typologie, perspectives’ (doctoral dissertation, École Pratique des Hautes Études, 2005), p. 172, specifically on the origin of Toledo 44.1.

⁹⁵ *P-Pm* Ms. 368, fols. 98^r-103^r; see Corbin, *Essai*, pp. 363-5. There is no rubric mentioning seasonal restrictions or precedence rules for this office; these may have been assumed from the general practice governing Marian Saturday offices, probably not far removed from that attested in Braga and Évora.

rubr	<i>Quere supra in officio beatæ mariæ cotidiano qui dicitur ante adventum.</i>
[Ad Matutinum]	
I	In honore beatissimæ Mariæ virginis jubilemus domino (001086) PS Venite (94)
H	Quem terra pontus æthera (008375)
In I noct.	
A1.1	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709) PS Domine dominus noster (8)
A1.2	Sicut myrrha electa (004942) PS Caeli enarrant (18)
A1.3	Haec est quæ nescivit (003001) PS Domini est terra (23)
W	Ave Maria gratia plena R. Dominus tecum (007958.1)
lect. 1	Loquamur aliquid de laudibus sacratissimæ Mariæ virginis ... scala caeli ianua paradisi. (pseudo-Bernard of Clairvaux, <i>Sermo de laudibus Mariæ virginis</i>)
R1.1	Ave festiva ferculi (600178)
V1	Monte Libano (600178a)
lect. 2	Eva si quidem tamquam arbor letifera ... sua immortalitas absorberet. (Id.)
R1.2	Videte miraculum matris (007869)
V1	Haec speciosum forma (007869za)
lect. 3	Quæsita est domicella per quam tanti sacramenti gratia ... et consummatio totius sanctitatis. (Id.)
R1.3	Ave gemma Christi (a06975)
V1	Regina caeli palatium (a06975a)
V2	Gloria patri (909000)
In II noct.	
A2.1	Specie tua et pulchritudine (004987) PS Eructavit (44)
A2.2	Dignare me laudare (002217) PS Deus noster refugium (45)
A2.3	Sicut lætantium (004936) PS Fundamenta (86)
W	Benedicta tu in mulieribus R. Et benedictus fructus ventris tuis (007971)
lect. 4	Haec et urna aurea ... et ipse fundavit eum altissimus. (Id.)
R2.1	Vulnerasti cor meum (a08511)
V1	Quam pulchrae sunt (a08511a)
lect. 5	Haec beatissima virgo Maria est aula regis ... nec est sancta ut Maria mater eius. (Id.)
R2.2	Ave porta Orientis (a08508)
V1	Ante partum virgo manens (a08508a)
lect. 6	O sacra et sanctissima virgo benedicta virgo Maria in nostræ necessitatibus ... per te suscipiat nos qui per te datus est nobis. (Id.)
R2.3	O quam pulchra es (a08503)
V1	Descendam in hortum meum (a08503a)
V2	Gloria patri (909000)
In III noct.	
A3.1	Gaude Maria virgo (002924) PS Cantate i° (95)
A3.2	In odorem unguentorum (003261) PS Dominus regnavit i° (96)
A3.3	Pulchra es et decora (004418) PS Cantate ii° (97)
W	Speciosa facta es et suavis R. In deliciis tuis sancta dei genitrix (008202)
lect. 7	<i>Secundum lucam</i> In illo tempore Loquente Jesu ad turbas: extollens vocem ... et ubera quæ suxisti (Luke 11:27). Et reliqua. <i>Omelia venerabilis bedæ presbiteri</i> Magnæ devotionis ac fidei hæc mulier ostenditur ... matri filium hominis fateri non debere dixerunt. (Bede, <i>In Lucae Evangelio Expositio</i> , IV, PL 92:479)
R3.1	Ad nutum domini (006024)
V1	Ut vitium virtus (006024a)
lect. 8	Set si caro verbi dei ... miraculo minime potuisset. (Id. PL 92:479-480)
R3.2	Hortus conclusus (601080)
V1	Fons hortorum puteus (601080a)

lect. 9	Set huic opinioni obstat ... qui audiunt verbum dei et custodiunt illud. (Id. PL 92:480)
R3.3	Cella redemptoris signo (<i>a08504</i>)
V1	Virgo Maria stella David (<i>a08504a</i>)
V2	Gloria (909000)
TD	Te deum laudamus
W	Ora pro nobis sancta dei genitrix (800319)
In Laudibus	
A1	Post partum virgo (004332) PS Dominus regnavit (92)
A2	Oculi tui sancta dei genitrix (004110) PS Jubilate (99)
A3	Maria virgo semper laetare (003708) PS Deus deus meus (62)
A4	Sub tuam protectionem (005040) Ca Benedicite
A5	Sub tuum praesidium (005041) PS Laudate (148)
cap	Ego quasi vitis ... fructus honoris et honestatis. (Eccles. 24:23)
H	O gloriosa domina (008375e)
W	Ora pro nobis sancta dei genitrix (800319)
B	Gaude dei genitrix virgo (002920.1)
or	Deus qui de beatae Mariae ... eius apud te intercessionibus adjuvemur.
Ad Primam	
A	Hortus conclusus es (003137.1) PS Deus in nomine tuo (53) <i>Cum reliquis</i>
cap	Regi autem ... [honor et gloria in saecula saeculorum.] (1 Tim. 1:17)
R	Jesu Christi filii dei vivi (601272)
V1	Qui natus es de virgine Maria (601272d)
V2	Gloria patri (909000)
W	Exurge domine adjuva nos (008072)
Ad Tertiam	
A	Sancta dei genitrix (004699.1) PS Legem pone (118:33)
cap	Et radicavi [in populo honorificato ... sanctorum detentio mea] (Eccles. 24:16)
R	Ora pro nobis (601702)
or	Deus qui salutis aeternae ... [auctorem vitae suscipe dominum nostrum.]
rubr	<i>Quere totum istud supra in cotidiana commemoratione horarum beatae Mariae.</i>
Ad Sextam	
A	In prole mater (003274) [PS Deficit in salutare (118:81)]
cap	Et sic in Syon ... [et in Jerusalem potestas mea] (Eccles. 24:15)
R	Sancta dei genitrix (007568)
or	Deus qui virginalem [aulam ... facias suae interesse festivitati.]
Ad Nonam	
A	Gaude Maria virgo (002924) PS Mirabilia (118:129)
cap	Quasi cedrus exaltata ... [quasi cypressus in monte Syon] (Eccles. 24:17)
R	Speciosa facta es (602225)
or	Famulorum tuorum ... [Jesu Christo intercessione salvemur.]
rubr	<i>Quere omnia ista hic ordinata ad horas diei ubi super in cotidiana commemoratione horarum beatae Mariae.</i>

Table 4. The nine-lesson Office in the breviary *P-Pm* Ms. 368.

The first rubric assumes that Vespers adopts its opening antiphon and psalmody from the pre-Advent daily Hours of the Virgin, namely the antiphon *Ave Maria gratia plena* (001539) and

the Friday ferial cursus.⁹⁶ Another possibility is that the opening antiphon and psalmody were taken from the feast assigned to the day, as may also have been the case in Évora. The office has no proper Compline or Second Vespers. The final rubric directs the reader instead to the daily Hours of the Virgin for the remaining material.⁹⁷ It further provides a series of six alternative lessons for Matins – ‘aliae lectiones de beata virgine dicende in sabbatis’ – to be followed by the same Bede’s homily, ‘Magnae devotionis’, on the lemma from Luke 11:27, with the responsories as in the main series – ‘evangelium. Et cetera alia ut supra’:⁹⁸

Lect. 1-6

Fuit in Toletana urbe quidam archiepiscopus qui vocabatur Ildefonsus ... eam honoraverit gratiam dei et suam obtinebit. (Poncelet, 590)

The homily ‘Loquamur aliquid de laudibus sacratissimae Mariae virginis’, here without a declared authorship but usually attributed to Bernard of Clairvaux, is the one prescribed as the reading for the Saturday Office of Our Lady in the Ordinal of Sibert of Beka, approved in 1312,⁹⁹ and subsequently used in the Carmelite breviary as the first six lessons for this office, followed by Bede’s ‘Magnae devotionis’.¹⁰⁰ To my knowledge, *P-Pm* Ms. 368 is the only Portuguese manuscript witness of this pseudo-Bernard homily.¹⁰¹

The alternative lessons consist of the complete legend known as ‘Hildefonsus’ (the first in the series of Marian miracles labelled *HM*), a narrative centred on the Virgin’s reward for devotion expressed through her praise and liturgical commemoration.¹⁰² Unlike the miracle lessons in the 1528 Évora breviary, the text in *P-Pm* Ms. 368 is quite close, though not identical, to the version in the Alcoaça *Mariale*,¹⁰³ suggesting dependence on different exemplars, deriving, in this case, from the same branch of the Marian miracle tradition.¹⁰⁴

This office compares with that in the aforementioned Évora breviary not only in its markedly devotional character but also in the number of shared chant pieces, pointing to a possibly

⁹⁶ *P-Pm* Ms. 368, fol. 93^v.

⁹⁷ *P-Pm* Ms. 368, fols. 93^v-94^v. Corbin, *Essai*, p. 363, states that the three alternative Magnificat antiphons given in Vespers are for Second Vespers, ‘selon le temps’.

⁹⁸ *P-Pm* Ms. 368, fols. 103^v-104^v.

⁹⁹ B. Zimmerman, *Ordinaire de l’Ordre de Notre-Dame du Mont-Carmel par Sibert de Beka (vers 1312) publié d’après le manuscrit original et collationé sur divers manuscrits et imprimés* (Paris, 1910), pp. 33-4.

¹⁰⁰ See, for example, *Breviarium Carmelitarum* (Venice: Lucantonio Giunta, 1515), fols. 65^r-66^v.

¹⁰¹ The text is not found in the modern editions of St Bernard’s works, but it had several editions in the early sixteenth century, for instance in the *Melliflui deuotique doctoris sancti Bernardi abbatis Clareuallensis Cisterciensis ordinis Opus preclarum suos complectens sermones de tempore* (Lyon: Johann Clein, 1515), fols. 126^v-127^r, with the title ‘Sermo de laudibus Mariae virginis’.

¹⁰² On this narrative, see Wilson, *The Stella maris*, pp. 190-1.

¹⁰³ *P-Ln* Alc. 149, fols. 21^r-22^r; see n. 57.

¹⁰⁴ Differences between the versions in *P-Ln* Alc. 149 and *P-Pm* Ms. 368 are limited to a few word transpositions, orthographic variants, and synonymic substitutions.

common background and to the roughly contemporary compilation of the offices themselves, despite the much later date of the surviving Évora printed witness. All the Matins and Lauds antiphons are the same and follow the same order in both sources, including the rare Benedictus antiphon in rhymed prose, *Gaude dei genitrix virgo* (002920.1);¹⁰⁵ the third Magnificat antiphon in *P-Pm* Ms. 368 (the only one in Braga), *Speciosa facta es* (206209), is the same as the Magnificat antiphon for Second Vespers in Évora;¹⁰⁶ and six Matins responsories in *P-Pm* Ms. 368 are common to Évora (three from the latter main series and three from the alternative series). The responsory *Vulnerasti cor meum* (a08511) – with its verse, ‘Quam pulchrae sunt’ (a08511a), a close quotation of Cant. 4:9-10 – is, to my knowledge, attested only in *P-Pm* Ms. 368,¹⁰⁷ and the same is true of the Vespers versicle *Beatam me dicent* (a08645), which appears to be a local paraphrastic reworking of Luke 1:48b-49. In turn, the responsory *Ave gemma Christi* (a06975) occurs in no other known Portuguese source.¹⁰⁸

4. Compiling the Offices

From the late twelfth century, votive and commemorative offices were typically assembled by borrowing from the proper repertory of related feasts in the sanctoral, with relatively few, if any, newly compiled or newly composed items. Some non-chant materials, particularly the lessons, were often drawn from available collections of devotional or exegetical writings rather than from the readings assigned to those feasts. This general model, however, requires refinement when tested against the internal concordance patterns of specific offices, that is, their recurrence elsewhere within the same source.¹⁰⁹ The internal concordance tables of the three- and nine-lesson *Cantica Canticorum* offices (as in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’, the earliest surviving witness of the complete Braga–Coimbra forms¹¹⁰) and of the nine-lesson Évora

¹⁰⁵ This antiphon is the seventh in the list of canticle antiphons for the days within the octave of the Assumption in Braga.

¹⁰⁶ The first and second Magnificat antiphons in *P-Pm* Ms. 368, *Alma redemptoris mater* (001356) and *Mater patris et filia* (205362), are also given in Évora for the day before the Sunday within the Octave of the Assumption as the Magnificat and Benedictus antiphons, respectively.

¹⁰⁷ An edition of its text is given in Appendix 1.

¹⁰⁸ The first attestation of this rare responsory seems to be the late twelfth-century antiphoner of Santa Cruz de la Serós (*E-Jmb* Ms. s.s., fol. 15^v), near San Juan de la Peña, both of which were female Benedictine monasteries in the province of Huesca. It is also included in the mid-thirteenth-century Gradual of Fontevraud (*F-LG* Ms. 2, fol. 272^{r-v}), which was in use at the Collegiate Church of Saint-Junien in the Diocese of Limoges after 1387.

¹⁰⁹ See Roper, ‘Medieval English Benedictine Liturgy’, vol. 1, pp. 206-29a, for discussion of the compilation of votive and commemorative offices, and vol. 2, pp. 68-72, for the internal concordance tables of the offices in the St Albans and Winchcombe breviaries.

¹¹⁰ The Coimbra ‘Liber catenatus’, although earlier, does not preserve the full structure of the nine-lesson office and, being a psalter-hymnal, lacks the complete sanctoral section required for concordance analysis.

office (as in the 1528 printed breviary), shown in Appendix 2, indicate that borrowing is not governed by a single uniform principle of sanctoral derivation, but operates through differentiated patterns of integration, ranging from the structurally layered organisation around the daily Hours of the Virgin characteristic of the Saturday offices in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’ to the more continuously distributed Marian repertorial borrowing of the Évora Saturday office. The Saturday office in the breviary *P-Pm* Ms. 368 cannot be included in this assessment, since this manuscript has no sanctoral section, which may have been contained in a separate volume, no longer extant.

The final rubric of the three-lesson Braga office in the ‘Fernão Duarte Breviary’ corroborates the patterns visible in the concordance table and the strategy underlying its compilation that presupposes cross-repertorial borrowing between offices: ‘Ad primam vero tertiam sextam et nonam dicantur omnia ut infra notatur in officio eiusdem virginis quod celebrantur a festo purificationis usque dominica in passione et a sequenti die post festum sancte trinitatis usque ad adventum domini. Responsorialia superposita quaere in nativitate eiusdem beatae mariae’ (‘At Prime, Terce, Sext, and None, everything is to be said as indicated below in the Office of the same Virgin, which is celebrated from the feast of the Purification until Passion Sunday, and from the day after Trinity Sunday until Advent. The responsories written above are to be taken from the Nativity of the same Blessed Mary’).¹¹¹ The office depends on the framework of the daily Hours of the Virgin, while the Matins responsories are taken sequentially from the series for the days within the octave of the Nativity of Our Lady. The Invitatory is borrowed from the Annunciation, whereas the canticle antiphons, together with some Matins antiphons, derive from the series for the days within the octave of the Assumption, as shown in the concordance table.¹¹² Vespers and Matins share the psalm antiphon. The hymns and versicles circulate across the wider Marian repertory, including the Purification, Annunciation, Assumption, and Nativity of Our Lady, from which much of the material of the daily Hours was drawn.

The nine-lesson office in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’ represents an organic expansion of the three-lesson office. Vespers and Lauds remain unchanged, except for the extension of the latter to a five-antiphon structure and the substitution of the Magnificat and Benedictus antiphons, while

¹¹¹ *E-E e-IV-10*, fols. 92^v-93^r.

¹¹² The prominent role of the Feast of the Assumption and the days within its octave in the compilation of Marian votive and commemorative offices has also been noted by Roper in relation to English sources; see her ‘Medieval English Benedictine Liturgy’, vol. 1, pp. 171-2, 174-6, 179, 206, 211-2, and 260. The feast with the reference ‘secundum hispanos’ in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’, most commonly titled ‘Commemoracione beatae Mariae virginis’, is a relic of the Old Hispanic feast of the Annunciation, celebrated on 18 December. In Braga, it follows the office of the Annunciation of 25 March, except for the Matins lessons.

Matins is reorganised from a single nocturn with a single psalm antiphon structure, characteristic of the daily Hours of the Virgin, into a full secular three-nocturn cursus, each nocturn following the standard pattern of three psalm antiphons. The original responsory series is retained in the first nocturn, together with the use of Gregory of Elvira's *Tractatus de Epithalamio* as the source for the lessons of the first two nocturns.¹¹³ The Lesser Hours remain the same as in the daily Hours of the Virgin.

The Matins antiphons exhibit a graded pattern of sequential borrowing across the three nocturns. The first nocturn shows block or sequential borrowing primarily from the Purification and, alternatively, from the series for the days within the octave of the Nativity of Our Lady, although the former is more likely, given the antiphons of the second nocturn; possible derivation from the series for the days within the octave of the Assumption and, in the case of the first antiphon, from the daily Hours remains secondary. The second nocturn continues with a largely near-sequential pattern of borrowing from the Purification. The third nocturn borrows from the series for the days within the octave of the Assumption, with its final antiphon also retained from the three-lesson office, together with one antiphon without concordance – the second, *Post partum virgo* (004332). The Invitatory antiphon, *In honore beatissimae Mariae* (001086), which replaces the Annunciation-derived Invitatory of the three-lesson office, also lacks concordance.

At Lauds, the structure combines retention and block borrowing. The first antiphon is preserved from the three-lesson office, also integrating the series for the days within the octave of the Assumption, from where it was originally borrowed. The second, third, and fifth antiphons are drawn from this series, whereas the fourth antiphon is taken specifically from Lauds of the Assumption, with possible derivation from the series for the days within the octave of the Nativity of Our Lady remaining secondary, introducing a layer of direct feast-based borrowing within the overall Assumption-derived block.

The responsories are largely drawn from the series for the days within the octave of the Nativity of Our Lady, with the first three preserved from the three-lesson office. Exceptions include the second responsory of the second nocturn, *Virginibus cunctis* (602498.1), which has no concordance, and the third responsory of the third nocturn, which is borrowed from the Nativity itself, as in the Lauds antiphons.

The canticle antiphons follow differentiated borrowing patterns. The substituted Benedictus antiphon and the newly introduced Magnificat antiphon of Second Vespers are drawn from

¹¹³ As noted above, the breviary known as the 'Valasco Breviary' is an exception, as it gives the Song of Songs in the second nocturn.

the series for the days within the octave of the Assumption, whereas the Magnificat antiphon of First Vespers, *Speciosa facta es et suavis* (206209), which replaces the corresponding antiphon of the three-lesson office, and the newly introduced *Nunc dimittis* antiphon of Compline, *Glorificamus te dei genitrix* (002952), have no internal concordance within the repertory of the ‘Soeiro Breviary’.

The final rubric in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’ explicitly corroborates the derivational logic identified in the concordance table and just described: ‘Istae antiphonae supradictae et responsoria require in assumptione beatae virginis et in nativitate eiusdem in mensis augusti et septembris’ (‘Seek the antiphons and responsories written above in the Assumption of the Blessed Virgin and in her Nativity in the months of August and September’).¹¹⁴ Taken together, these concordance patterns reveal four principal layers of borrowing within the nine-lesson *Cantica Canticorum* Office: the inherited framework of the daily Hours of the Virgin; the Purification as the principal source for the Matins antiphons; the series for the days within the octave of the Assumption, together with the Assumption itself, as the dominant source for the Lauds and canticle antiphons, and as a complementary layer within the Matins antiphons; and the series for the days within the octave of the Nativity of Our Lady, together with the Nativity itself, as the principal structuring source for the responsory series. Alongside these layers, the five chant items without internal concordance within the ‘Soeiro Breviary’ indicate the selective incorporation of materials derived through external processes that fall outside the internal borrowing logic of the compilation, understood here as a Braga-centred logic of selection within a repertory that may have been shared with Coimbra in earlier stages of transmission.

Among this small group, the responsory *Virginibus cunctis* is of particular relevance, since its documented dissemination is quite limited. Its presence in the Braga nine-lesson office may reflect the incorporation of material belonging to a Coimbra-centred node of transmission.¹¹⁵

The antiphons *Speciosa facta es et suavis* and *Post partum virgo* are also attested in the use of Évora, which frequently corresponds with Coimbra. Their presence in the Braga office may be explained as the retention of elements belonging to the same Coimbra-related tradition, also preserved in Évora.

The two remaining items – the canticle antiphon *Glorificamus te dei genitrix* and the Invitatory *In honore beatissimae Mariae* – are more problematic. The first is attested in English uses, including Sarum and Worcester, as well as in the Low Countries and the

¹¹⁴ *P-BRad* Ms. 657, fol. 176^v.

¹¹⁵ See above, pp. 12-4.

Germanic area, with no known French or Iberian witnesses other than Braga and Coimbra. The second seems to show a similar overall distribution, though extending into northern France and only marginally into northern Italy, with several attestations in relatively late votive and commemorative Marian offices, for instance in the daily Hours of the Virgin included in books of hours.¹¹⁶ It also has at least one early attestation in the late-eleventh-century breviary of Santo Domingo de Silos (*GB-Lbl* Add MS 30849, fol. 266^v), where it is assigned to the Nativity of Our Lady. In both cases, the evidence points less to a traceable line of transmission than to participation in a broader, modular Marian repertory circulating within the tradition of the Hours of the Virgin.¹¹⁷

These residual cases should nevertheless be set against the evidence of the nine-lesson office in the 1528 Évora breviary, which exhibits a comparable but independently organised pattern of repertorial selection within the Saturday Office of Our Lady. Its repertory draws extensively on the daily Hours of the Virgin ('De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae'), including its seasonal variations, while additional material is distributed across chants shared with Marian feasts (especially the Purification, Assumption, and Conception of the Virgin) and the Common of One Virgin; the contribution of the Psalter section of the breviary is minimal, comprising only three items.

The Matins antiphons exhibit a graded pattern of borrowing across the three nocturns, moving from block and sequential borrowing from the Purification in the first nocturn, to a second and third nocturn in which Purification-derived material remains dominant but is increasingly combined with borrowings from the Common of One Virgin, the latter contributing a single antiphon in the second nocturn and two antiphons in the third nocturn.

The responsories exhibit a tripartite pattern of organisation. The first nocturn is characterised by block and sequential borrowing from the series for the days within the octave of the Assumption. The second nocturn continues this reliance on the same series, but in a more fragmented form, combining block and near-sequential borrowings with a responsory without concordance (*Stella maris fulget*), which is otherwise unattested. The third nocturn displays a

¹¹⁶ On the *Late Medieval and Renaissance Illuminated Manuscripts – Books of Hours 1300-1530* website (CHD – Center for Håndskriftstudier i Danmark), IV. *Hours of the Virgin* (last updated 2007), at <<https://www.manuscripts.org.uk/chd.dk/tutor/index.html#hv>>, in relation to the daily Hours of the Virgin, the Invitatory *In honore* is assigned to Germany and the northern Netherlands, whereas the antiphon *Glorificamus te* is classified as 'common'. For southern France and Portugal, the antiphon given is *Speciosa facta es*, in the latter case on the basis of the 1494 Braga breviary and the *Breviarium secundum vsuum insignis monasterij sancte crucis colibriensis ordinis diui augustini* (Coimbra: German Gaillard, 1531).

¹¹⁷ See Stutzmann and Chevalier, 'Books of hours as codified compilations', on the modular and recombinatory nature of books of hours and their implications for patterns of textual circulation, especially pp. 154-75 on the Hours of the Virgin.

more heterogeneous configuration, combining a responsory shared with several Marian feasts, one drawn from the daily Hours of the Virgin, and *Ad nutum domini*, without internal concordance in Évora, although attested in Portuguese sources, for instance in Braga. Of the two responsories in the alternative series that have concordances, one is drawn from the Assumption and the other is shared across several Marian feasts, including the daily Hours of the Virgin, a pattern similar to that observed in the third nocturn of the main series.¹¹⁸

The Lauds antiphons display a more dispersed pattern of borrowing than the preceding sections. The first antiphon is drawn from the daily Hours of the Virgin. The second and fourth antiphons have no concordance in Évora, although both are attested elsewhere in Portuguese sources, including Braga. The third antiphon is associated primarily with the Assumption, being used in its memorial within the Octave of St Lawrence, while the fifth antiphon brings together a denser cluster of concordances spanning the Purification, Visitation, Assumption, Conception, and Annunciation, thus condensing within a single position a broader Marian repertorial field.

The canticle antiphons follow a distinct pattern of borrowing. The Benedictus antiphon and the Magnificat antiphon of Second Vespers are drawn from the series for the days within the octave of the Assumption. By contrast, the Magnificat antiphon of First Vespers, *Speciosa facta es et suavis*, has no internal concordance in the Évora repertory, although it is also attested in the Braga office of the ‘Soeiro Breviary’. These do not appear to constitute a coherent structural layer, but rather reflect borrowing that combines chants from a specific Marian office with isolated items of wider dissemination.

Unlike the nine-lesson office in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’, the Évora office does not articulate a stratified system of repertorial borrowing, but instead exhibits a continuous pattern of selection in which established structures, feast-based material – especially from the days within the octave of the Assumption – and locally attested chants are integrated within a single compositional logic without hierarchical ordering of repertorial sources.

The comparison of the offices in the Évora and the *P-Pm* Ms. 368 breviaries reveals a complete identity of the ordered antiphonal cursus at both Matins and Lauds. At Matins, all three nocturns transmit the same sequence of antiphons in the same order across both witnesses. The Lauds antiphons present an identical cursus in both offices (see Appendix 3). This structural concordance extends to the psalmodic cursus within the Saturday Office, where Évora and *P-Pm* Ms. 368 display an identical arrangement, except at Prime, in contrast

¹¹⁸ On the responsories in the Évora Saturday office, see above, pp. 23-4.

to the ‘Soeiro Breviary’, whose divergence from Évora includes the Little Hours, while its divergence from *P-Pm* Ms. 368 is confined to Terce, Sext, and None (see Appendix 4). These differences derive from differently organised but stable configurations of the daily Hours of the Virgin and the ferial office. The close correspondence between Évora and *P-Pm* Ms. 368 gains additional significance when set against the Coimbra-centred liturgical profile of the latter manuscript.¹¹⁹ Its implications become clearer when considered alongside the Braga–Coimbra nine-lesson office, whose first nocturn and part of the second also preserve the same ordered antiphonal series. The three offices thus share a common structural core, even though their larger organisation varies between them. Rather than pointing to simple linear dependence, these correspondences suggest participation in a shared network of transmission in which common repertorial materials circulated alongside multiple principles of organisation. Within this network, some sections of the office could remain stabilised across different uses, while others were recombined, redistributed, or expanded according to local compositional strategies and exegetical or devotional concerns.

This model is further corroborated by a fragment from a late fourteenth-century Portuguese antiphoner preserved in Coimbra, which transmits portions of a Marian office for Eastertide.¹²⁰ Although not fully aligned with the examined Saturday Office traditions, it exhibits substantial correspondences with them and reflects the same underlying tendency toward selective recombination of Song of Songs antiphons within a structured framework of the daily Hours and the ferial office. Its origin remains uncertain, but its present location

¹¹⁹ For a discussion of *P-Pm* Ms. 368, see above, pp. 24-9.

¹²⁰ *P-Cug* MM 1063 (57), reproduced, briefly described, and indexed on PEM, at <<https://pemdatabse.eu/source/99000>>. Its contents are as follows:

[Ad Laudes]

[B] [Quam pulchra es et quam decora ...] et ubera tua ... ibi dabo tibi ubera mea alleluia (004436)

[or] Deus qui de beatae Mariae [... eius apud te intercessionibus adiuvemur.]

[Ad Primam]

[H] Jam lucis orto* (008328)

[A] [Ho]rtus conclusus (202263) *psalmi consueti* [notation not entered]

[cap] Regi autem saeculorum (1 Tim. 1:17)

[R] Jesu Christe filii dei vivi* (006276)

[V] Qui natus es de virgine Maria* (006276ze)

[W] Exurge deus <ad>iuva nos* (008072)

[or] Deus qui verbum tuum [... eius etiam participes efficiamini natura.]

[Ad Tertiam]

[H] Nunc sancte nobis spiritus* (008354)

[A] [S]ancta dei genitrix (004699.1)

The content of Prime (the only complete section) is identical to that of the Seville breviaries, except for the collect. Traces of the Toledo–Seville tradition have also been identified in fragments preserved in the Municipal Archive of Loulé, in the Algarve; see M. P. Ferreira and Z. Chaves, ‘Fragmentos sonoros em Loulé: Vestígios de vivências religiosas medievais’, in *Atas do II Encontro de História de Loulé* (Loulé, 2019), pp. 223-41.

renders a Coimbra milieu plausible. The overall correspondence with the antiphonal sequences identified in Braga, Évora, and *P-Pm* Ms. 368 is substantial, differing only in the Benedictus antiphon at Lauds, *Quam pulchra es et quam decora* (004436), while preserving the Prime and Terce antiphons.¹²¹ This limited variation does not disrupt the broader configuration but rather reinforces the stability of the shared antiphonal framework within that network of transmission.

Final Remarks

Preliminary comparison with geographically and liturgically close uses, such as those centred on Toledo and its derivatives in Seville and Jaén,¹²² reveals instructive parallels in feast-borrowing, such as the Matins responsories taken from the days within the octave of the Nativity of Our Lady,¹²³ and a close structural integration with the daily Hours of the Virgin and the ferial office, even sharing with the Portuguese tradition the series of antiphons for the Little Hours. Toledo and its related diocesan uses in Andalusia, however, preserved the three-lesson form, combining a stable central repertorial structure with seasonally variable elements and seasonal restrictions on the celebration of the office itself, whereas the Portuguese offices lack such seasonal variations and are subject only to seasonal restrictions. While the set of psalm antiphons is common and ultimately derived from the Cluniac tradition embodied in the antiphoner Toledo 44.2, some of the canticle antiphons and a small number of other chant pieces are absent from known Portuguese sources and are apparently attested only locally or chiefly in Aragonese sources.¹²⁴ The Matins lessons also reveal wider patterns of transmission: the Marian devotional-homiletic prose characteristic of the Toledo tradition also circulated in British monastic and secular uses.¹²⁵ This evidence reflects partially overlapping

¹²¹ The fragment is the only known Portuguese witness to the antiphon *Quam pulchra es et quam decora*. The corresponding PEM entry, at <<https://pemdatabase.eu/musical-item/99029>>, notes that the antiphon's 'melodic version is currently not found in any other digitised Cantus source'.

¹²² Among the sources consulted for this comparison are the following: *E-Mn* Mss/8902, breviary from Toledo, adapted to the use of the Convent of Uclés, fifteenth century; [*Toledo brev.*]; *E-Mn* Mss/9694, breviary, unidentified location in Castile, fifteenth century; *E-Mn* Mss/6086, breviary, *pars sanctoralis*, Seville, fourteenth century; *F-Pn* lat. 982, breviary, Seville, third quarter of the fifteenth century (c.1462); *Breviarium secundum consuetudinem sancte ecclesie Gienensis* (Seville: Jacob Cromberger, 1528).

¹²³ 1. *Ad nutum domini*; 2. *Candida virginitas*; 3. *Ave festiva ferculi*.

¹²⁴ These include the Magnificat antiphon *Ave magna misericordiae* (200457) in the Toledo and Seville breviaries, the Benedictus antiphon *Exsulta satis Abraham fidelis* (a08586) in the Toledo and Jaén breviaries, as well as the alternative third responsory for Eastertide, *Emissiones tuae paradisi* (600779), in the Toledo, Seville, and Jaén breviaries.

¹²⁵ The lessons are as follows, in the reading of the [*Toledo brev.*]: 1. 'O alma virgo Maria tanto cunctis angelorum ... ad placandam iram venturi iudicis invenimus'; 2. 'Surge ergo o sancta virgo misericorditer actura pro nobis ... quod orando abolere non possis'; 3. 'O sacratissima virgo Maria nos qui hoc credimus ... quod servi filii tui domini nostri Jesu Christi effici mereamur'. Versions of these texts are found in the twelfth-century St

liturgical networks characterised by a shared core repertory and divergent peripheral transmission, with similar strategies of borrowing and source selection in the Portuguese and Toledo traditions, in contrast to different borrowing patterns and source dependency in the British uses.¹²⁶

The examination undertaken here shows that the Portuguese Saturday Offices of Our Lady emerge as products of intersecting liturgical and textual traditions shaped through selective borrowing, adaptation, and recombination. The surviving sources reveal both continuity and variation within a shared Marian repertorial culture extending across the Iberian Peninsula and beyond the Pyrenees, preserving distinct local configurations that reflect institutional context and evolving liturgical and devotional practices.

Albans and Winchcombe breviaries (Roper, 'Medieval English Benedictine Liturgy', vol. 2, pp. 68 and 71), the fifteenth-century book of hours of Barking Abbey (Yardley, 'Commemorating the Virgin Mary', p. 86), the *Ordinale Exon. (Exeter Chapter MS. 3502 Collated with Parker MS. 93)*, ed. J. N. Dalton, vol. 2 (London, 1909), p. 490, and the *Breviarium ad usum insignis ecclesiae Sarum*, II (Canterbury, 1882), cols. 305-6. They also appear in *E-Mn Mss/240*, breviary, Order of Santiago, Convent of Uclés, fifteenth century, as lessons 1-3 of the Saturday Office of Our Lady; and in A. Manrique, *Cisterciensium seu verius ecclesiasticorum annalium a condito Cistercio*, Tomus quartus (Lyon, 1659), pp. 555-6, where, on the authority of the 'old breviaries' of Palencia, Cuenca, and Salamanca, they are attributed with reservation to Bernard of Clairvaux.

¹²⁶ In the compilation of the St Albans and Winchcombe offices, Roper identifies a marked reliance on borrowing from Marian feasts, especially the Assumption, together with additional material drawn from the Annunciation and the Nativity. Texts from other sections of the sanctoral appear only occasionally. She also notes the incorporation of a small number of probably newly composed items. Her concordance tables further suggest that the daily Hours or the ferial office had little, if any, influence on the compilation of these offices. See Roper, 'Medieval English Benedictine Liturgy', vol. 1, pp. 167-76, and vol. 2, pp. 68-72.

Appendix 1. An Edition of the Unique Responsories in the 1528 Évora Breviary and *P-Pm* Ms. 368

The texts are presented with minimal punctuation added to clarify sentence structure. Orthography and capitalisation have been normalised for consistency.

Évora alternative series

1.1

(2.3 in *P-Pm* Ms. 368)

℞. O quam pulchra es, amica mea,
o quam pulchra es, oculi tui columbarum.
℣. Descendam in hortum meum
et vocabo sponsam meam,
et dicam ei: surge, propera.

Form: accentual verses with parallelism

Text source: Close quotation of Cant. 4:1, with verbal echo of Cant. 2:10

1.2

(3.3 in *P-Pm* Ms. 368)

℞. Cella Redemptoris, signo suscepta pudoris, quae genitrix Christi vere fieri meruisti, esto memor nostri reprimendo prelia monstri.
℣. Virgo Maria, stella David, de stirpe puella.

Form: rhymed prose

Text source: non-scriptural composition with Marian theological imagery

Variants (*P-Pm* Ms. 368):

‘signo suscepta’ > ‘signo subscripta’ (non-grammatical scribal reinterpretation or misreading)

‘Virgo Maria’ > ‘Virgo maris’ (scribal misreading of Marian title)

1.3

℞. Ave, vulnerata charitate, in medio uberum habens dilecti sepultum, ob mortis amaro redolens myrrhe fasciculum.
℣. Sepulti resurrectio sit tibi, botro cipri dulcior, dum gaudet fonte Dei Engadi, in gratia balsami fedos volentes lavari.

Form: rhymed prose

Text source: Centonised reworking of Cant. 1:13-14 with Christological expansion

2.2

℞. Ego dilecta, languero prae amore nimio; lectulus noster floribus, Dominus nostra cedrina et argenteae Salomonis columnae.
℣. Filiae Jerusalem, nuntiate dilecto meo, quia amore eius languero.

Form: rhymed prose

Text source: Composition with verbal quotation of Cant. 5:8 and centonised reuse of Cant. 1:16-17

2.3
(2.2 in *P-Pm* Ms. 368)

℞. Ave, porta Orientis, semper clausa; ex te mundus justitiae solem vidit ortum, cuncta simul continentem, ex conceptu genuisti.
 √. Ante partum virgo manens, et in partu perseverans, ac post partum incorrupta.

Form: rhymed prose

Text source: non-scriptural composition with typological references to Ezek. 44:2 and Mal. 4:2

Variants (*P-Pm* Ms. 368):

‘ex conceptu’ > ‘tu contentum’ (likely scribal corruption)

‘et in partu’ > ‘in partu’ (omission of conjunction)

3.1

℞. Stella maris, miserans miseris,
 confer medicinam,
 ne propriis pereant patiendo ruinam.
 Ut sicut puerum sine patre virgo Deum genuisti,
 sic puteum tere sulfureum,
 mater pia Christi.
 √. Frange cathenas mortis,
 habenas cuspide digna;
 pande superni limina regni,
 clave benigna.

Form: accentual verses with internal rhyme

Text source: non-scriptural composition with Marian devotional imagery

3.3

℞. Pulchrae sunt genae tuae, amica mea, ut turturis; collum tuum sicut monilia. Introducam te in vineam, et colligemus mala punica.
 √. Revertere, revertere, Sunamitis, revertere, ut intueamur te.

Form: rhymed prose

Text source: Close paraphrase of Cant. 1:10 and quotation of Cant. 6:13

***P-Pm* Ms. 368 series**

2.1

℞. Vulnerasti cor meum, soror mea, in uno oculorum tuorum, in uno crine colli tui.
 √. Quam pulchrae sunt mammae tuae, soror mea sponsa; pulchriora ubera tua vino.

Form: plain prose

Text source: close quotation of Cant. 4:9-10, with only minor omission

Appendix 2. Internal Concordances

Items given in the sources as incipits are marked with an asterisk; items inferred or derived from rubrics are given in square brackets.

Ad Vesperas		
A	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)*	Assumptio Mariae infra oct., V, M De BMV, N
cap	Beata es Maria quae dominum	De BMV, V
H	Ave maris stella (008272)*	Purificatio Mariae, V, V2 Annuntiatio Mariae, V, V2 Assumptio Mariae vig., V Assumptio Mariae, V2 Assumptio Mariae infra oct., V Nativitas Mariae, V, V2 Nativitas Mariae infra oct., V Annuntiatio Mariae secundum hispanos, V, V2 De BMV, V2 De BMV Adv., V2
W	Elegit eam deus (008046.2)*	Purificatio Mariae, V, L, S, V2 Assumptio Mariae vig., V Assumptio Mariae, L, V2 Nativitas Mariae, V, L, V2 Nativitas Mariae infra oct., V Memorials De BMV De BMV, V
M	Ave regina caelorum (001542.1)	Assumptio Mariae infra oct., ad B, ad M
or	Concede nos famulos tuos	Memorials De BMV De BMV, L
Ad Matutinum		
I	Ave Maria gratia plena (001042)	Annuntiatio Mariae, M Annuntiatio Mariae secundum hispanos, M
H	Quem terra pontus (008375)*	Purificatio Mariae, M Annuntiatio Mariae, M Assumptio Mariae, M Assumptio Mariae infra oct., M Nativitas Mariae, M Nativitas Mariae infra oct., M Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., M Annuntiatio Mariae secundum hispanos, M De BMV, M
In noct.		
A	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)*	This office, V
W	Speciosa facta es (008202)	Purificatio Mariae, M, N Assumptio Mariae, M Nativitas Mariae, M, N Nativitas Mariae infra oct., M Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., M De BMV, M, N
lect. 1-3	<i>Tres lectiones ... de canticis canticorum</i> (Greg. <i>Epithalamium</i> , 1:1-2, 4)	No concordance

R1-3	1 Stirps Jesse (007709) Virgo dei genitrix (007709a) 2 Ad nutum domini (006024) Ut vitium virtus (006024a) 3 Candida virginitas (006262) Quae meruit dominum (006262a)	Nativitas Mariae infra oct., M, R4-6
TD	Te deum laudamus (909010)*	Many concordances
[W	Ora pro nobis sancta dei (800319)]	Memorials De BMV De BMV
In Laudibus		
A	Sub tuam protectionem (005040)	Assumptio Mariae infra oct., M, V A15 De BMV, L
cap	Ego quasi vitis (Eccles. 24:23)	Purificatio Mariae, S De BMV, L
H	O gloriosa domina (008375e.1)*	Purificatio Mariae, L Annuntiatio Mariae, L Assumptio Mariae, L Nativitas Mariae, L Annuntiatio Mariae secundum hispanos, L De BMV Adv., L
W	Elegit eam deus (008046.2)*	This office, V
B	Anima mea liquefacta est (001418)	Assumptio Mariae infra oct., ad B, ad M
or	Concede nos famulos tuos*	This office, V
Ad Primam, Tertiam, Sextam et Nonam		De BMV

Table 1. The three-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum* in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’.

Ad Vesperas		
A	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)*	Assumptio Mariae infra oct., V, M De BMV, N 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , V, M
cap	Beata es Maria quae dominum*	De BMV, V 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , V
H	Ave maris stella (008272)*	Purificatio Mariae, V, V2 Annuntiatio Mariae, V, V2 Assumptio Mariae vig., V Assumptio Mariae, V2 Assumptio Mariae infra oct., V Nativitas Mariae, V, V2 Nativitas Mariae infra oct., V Annuntiatio Mariae secundum hispanos, V, V2 De BMV, V2 De BMV Adv., V2 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , V
W	Elegit eam deus (008046.2)*	Purificatio Mariae, V, L, S, V2 Assumptio Mariae vig., V Assumptio Mariae, L, V2 Nativitas Mariae, V, L, V2 Nativitas Mariae infra oct., V Memorials De BMV De BMV, V 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , V, L

M	Speciosa facta es et suavis (206209)	No concordance
or	Concede nos famulos tuos*	Memorials De BMV De BMV, L 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , V, L
[Ad Completorium]		
N	Glorificamus te dei genitrix (002952)	No concordance
[Ad Matutinum]		
I	In honore beatissimae (001086)	No concordance
H	Quem terra pontus (008375)*	Purificatio Mariae, M Annuntiatio Mariae, M Assumptio Mariae, M Assumptio Mariae infra oct., M Nativitas Mariae, M Nativitas Mariae infra oct., M Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., M Annuntiatio Mariae secundum hispanos, M De BMV, M 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , M
In I noct.		
A1-3	1 Benedicta tu (001709)* 2 Sicut myrrha electa (004942)* 3 Haec est quae nescivit (003001)*	Purificatio Mariae, M A1-3 Assumptio Mariae infra oct., M, V A3-4, 6 Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., M A1-3 A1 De BMV, M A1 De BMV Adv., M
W	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (007971)*	Purificatio Mariae, M Assumptio Mariae, M, T Nativitas Mariae, M, T Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., M De BMV, M, T De BMV Adv., N
lect. 1-3	1 Audistis epithalamium* [2 Sponsum autem Christum] [3 Denique ut sciatis]	3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , M lect. 1-3
R1-3	1 Stirps Jesse (007709)* 2 Ad nutum domini (006024)* 3 Candida virginitas (006262)*	Nativitas Mariae infra oct., M R4-6 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , M R1-3
In II noct.		
A4-6	4 Speciosa facta es (004988)* 5 Dignare me laudare (002217)* 6 Sicut laetantium (004936)*	Purificatio Mariae, M A4-5, 8
W	Sicut myrrha electa (008197)*	Purificatio Mariae, M Assumptio Mariae, M Nativitas Mariae, M, T Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., M De BMV, M, S
lect. 4-6	[4 Haec ergo ecclesia] [5 Ecclesia enim ut Apostolos] [6 Cuius origo terrena est]	No concordance
R4-6	4 Virginis electae (602499.1)* 5 Virginibus cunctis (602498.1) Cuius ventre deus jacuit (602498a) 6 Hortus conclusus (601080)*	Nativitas Mariae infra oct., M R7 R5 No concordance Nativitas Mariae infra oct., M R9
In III noct.		

A7-9	7 Oculi tui sancta dei (004110)* 8 Post partum virgo (004332)* 9 Gaude Maria virgo (002924)*	A7 Assumptio Mariae infra oct., M, V Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., M A8 No concordance A9 Assumptio Mariae infra oct., M, V De BMV, N 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , V, M
W	Speciosa (008202)*	Purificatio Mariae, M, N Assumptio Mariae, M Nativitas Mariae, M, N Nativitas Mariae infra oct., M Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., M De BMV 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , M
lect. 7-9	7 Loquente Jesu ad turbas: extollens [Magnae devotionis] [8 Nam sicut tunc Judei] [9 Verum consubstantialemque]	Assumptio Mariae vig., M lect. 1-3
R7-9	7 Ave festiva ferculi (600178)* 8 Virga dedit florem (a00365)* 9 Felix valde es (600873.1)*	R7-8 Nativitas Mariae infra oct., M R12, 11 R9 Nativitas Mariae, M R9 Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., M R9
TD	Te deum laudamus (909010)*	Many concordances 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , M
W	Ora pro nobis (800319)*	Memorials De BMV De BMV 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , M
In Laudibus		
A1-5	1 Sub tuam protectionem (005040)* 2 Hortus conclusus (003137.1)* 3 Sancta dei genitrix (004699.1)* 4 In odorem unguentorum (003261)* 5 Sub tuum praesidium (005041)*	A1 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , L De BMV, L A1-3, 5 Assumptio Mariae infra oct., M, V A15, 17, 12, 16 A4 Assumptio Mariae, L Nativitas Mariae Dom. infra oct., V
cap	Ego quasi vitis (Eccles. 24:23)*	Purificatio Mariae, S De BMV, L 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , L
H	O gloriosa domina (008375e.1)*	Purificatio Mariae, L Annuntiatio Mariae, L Assumptio Mariae, L Nativitas Mariae, L Annuntiatio Mariae secundum hispanos, L De BMV Adv., L 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , L
W	Elegit eam deus (008046.2)*	3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , L This office, V
B	Ave spes nostra dei (001546)*	Assumptio Mariae infra oct., ad B, ad M
or	Concede nos famulos tuos*	Memorials De BMV De BMV, L 3-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i> , V, L This office, V
Ad [Primam], Tertiam, Sextam et Nonam		De BMV
Ad II Vesperas		

A1-5	[1 Benedicta tu (001709)] [2 Sicut myrrha electa (004942)] [3 Haec est quae nescivit (003001)] [4 Speciosa facta es (004988)] [5 Dignare me laudare (002217)]	This office, M
cap	Beata es Maria*	This office, V
H	Ave maris stella (008272)*	This office, V
W	Elegit eam (008046.2)*	This office, V
M	Ave gloriosa dei (200455.1)*	Assumptio Mariae infra oct., ad B, ad M
or	[Concede nos famulos tuos]	This office, V

Table 2. The nine-lesson Office *Cantica Canticorum* in the ‘Soeiro Breviary’.

Ad Vesperas		
[A	Ave Maria gratia plena (001539)]	Adv. hebd. 3, fer. 4, P Annuntiatio Mariae, L De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, V De BMV Adv., T
cap	Sicut cinamomum (Eccles. 24:20)	De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, V
R	Hortus conclusus (601080)*	This office, M
H	Ave maris stella (008272)*	Purificatio Mariae, V Annuntiatio Mariae, V Assumptio Maria vig., V Conceptio Mariae, V, V2 De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, V De BMV Adv., V2 De BMV post Epiph., V2
W	Beatam me dicent (800039)	Epiphania infra oct., Memoria BMV Purificatio Mariae, V Assumptio Maria vig., V De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, V
M	Ave regina caelorum (001542.1)	Assumptio Mariae infra octv., V ad M
or	Concede nos famulos*	De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, V
Ad Completorium		
A	Dignare me laudare (002217)*	Purificatio Mariae, M, C Annuntiatio Mariae, C Visitatio Mariae, C Assumptio Maria, C Assumptio Maria infra oct., M Conceptio Mariae, C De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, C
cap	Tu autem (Jer. 14:9)*	Sabb. per annum, C
H	Te lucis (008399)*	Sabb. per annum, C Nativitas Domini vig., C Epiphania, C Quadragesima Dom. 1, C Feria 4 Maj. Hebd., C Dom. in Albis, C Visitatio Mariae, C

W	Custodi nos (008001)*	Sabb. per annum, C Nativitas Domini vig., C Feria 4 Maj. Hebd., C Dom. in Albis, C
N	Sub tuum praesidium (005041)*	Purificatio Mariae, C Annuntiatio Mariae, C Visitatio Mariae, C Assumptio Maria, C Conceptio Mariae, C
or	Visita quaesumus*	Sabb. per annum, C
Ad Matutinum		
I	In honore beatissimae (001086)	No concordance
H	Quem terra (008375)*	Purificatio Mariae, M Annuntiatio Mariae, M Assumptio Maria, M Conceptio Mariae, M De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, M De BMV Adv., M De BMV post Epiph., M
In I noct.		
A1-3	1 Benedicta tu (001709) 2 Sicut myrrha electa (004942) 3 Haec est quae nescivit (003001)	Purificatio Mariae, M A1-3 Other concordances for each individual A
W	Diffusa est gratia (008014)*	Many concordances
lect. 1-3	1 Sollemnem memoriam 2 Denique dum illi exanimis 3 Beata itaque virgo Maria	No concordance
R1-3	1 Ave festiva ferculi (600178) 2 Hortus conclusus (601080) 3 Solem justitiae regem (007677)	Assumptio Maria infra oct., M R1-3 Other concordances for R2
In II noct.		
A4-6	4 Specie tua (004987) 5 Dignare me laudare (002217) 6 Sicut laetantium (004936)	A4 Comm. unius Virginis, M A4 A5 Purificatio Mariae, M A5 Other concordances A6 Purificatio Mariae, M A8 De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, M
W	Specie tua (008201)*	Many concordances
lect. 4-6	4 Adducatur et alius miser 5 Et si haec preconia 6 Salve inquam ave gloriosum	No concordance
R4-6	4 Virga dedit florem (a00365) 5 Stirps Jesse (007709) 6 Stella maris fulget (a06932)	R4-5 Assumptio Maria infra oct., M R4, 6 R5 also Annae R6 No concordance
In III noct.		
A7-9	7 Gaude Maria virgo (002924) 8 In odorem unguentorum (003261) 9 Pulchra es et decora (004418)	A7 Purificatio Mariae, M A7 A8-9 Comm. unius Virginis, M A9, 8 Other concordances for each individual A
W	Adjuvabit eam (007934)*	Many concordances
lect. 7-9	7 Loquente Jesu ad turbas: extollens Unigenitus dei charissimi 8 At ille dixit: quinimmo 9 O veneranda domina electa	No concordance

R7-9	Post partum virgo (007400) Ora pro nobis (601702) Ad nutum domini (006024)	R7 Purificatio Mariae, S Visitatio Mariae, N Assumptio Mariae, N Conceptio Mariae, S R8 De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, T R9 No concordance
TD	Te deum laudamus (909010)*	Many concordances
W	Ora pro nobis (800319)*	Dom. Resurrectionis, C Pasc. hebd. 2 fer. 2, L De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, M
Alternative lect. 1-9 (see main text)		No concordance
Alternative R1-3, 5-7, and 9 (see main text)		No concordance
Alternative R4 Candida virginitas (006262)		Assumptio Mariae, M R9
Alternative R8 Ave Maria gratia plena (006155)		Purificatio Mariae, T Anuntiatio Mariae, T Assumptio Mariae, S De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, P
In Laudibus		
A1-5	1 Post partum virgo (004332) 2 Oculi tui sancta dei (004110) 3 Maria virgo semper (003708) 4 Sub tuam protectionem (005040) 5 Sub tuum praesidium (005041)	A1 De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, L A2 No concordance A3 Laurentii oct., Memoria Assumpt. Mariae A4 No concordance A5 Purificatio Mariae, C Visitatio Mariae, C Assumptio Mariae, C Conceptio Mariae, C Anuntiatio Mariae, C
cap	Ego quasi vitis (Eccles. 24:23)*	De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, L
H	O gloriosa (008375e)*	Purificatio Mariae, L Anuntiatio Mariae, L Assumptio Mariae, L Conceptio Mariae, L De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, L De BMV Adv., L De BMV post Epiph., L
W	Elegit eam deus (008046.2)*	Stephani oct., Memoria BMV Anuntiatio Mariae, L De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, L
B	Gaude dei genitrix virgo (002920.1)	No concordance
or	Deus qui de beatae Mariae*	De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, L
Ad Primam		
A	Hortus conclusus es (003137.1)*	De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae, P
cap	Regi autem (1 Tim. 1:17)*	Dom. per annum, P
R	Jesu Christi (601272)*	Many concordances
or	In hac hora*	Dom. per annum, P
Ad Tertiam, Sextam et Nonam		De BMV sec. usum Elborensis ecclesiae
Ad II Vesperas		
A1-5	1 Benedicta tu (001709)* 2 Sicut myrrha electa (004942)* 3 Haec est quae nescivit (003001)* 4 In odorem unguentorum (003261)* 5 Pulchra es et decora (004418)*	This office, M
cap	[Sicut cinamomum (Eccles. 24:20)]	This office, V
H	[Ave maris stella (008272)]	This office, V

W	[Beatam me dicent (800039)]	This office, V
M	Speciosa facta es (206209)	No concordance
or	[Concede nos famulos]	This office, V

Table 3. The Saturday Office of Our Lady in the 1528 Évora breviary.

Appendix 3. Series of Antiphons and Matins Responsories in the Nine-Lesson Saturday Office of Our Lady

Incipits in italics correspond to pieces identified in the source following rubrical indications.

Antiphons

	'Soeiro Breviary'	1528 Évora breviary	P-Pm Ms. 368
Ad Vesperas			
A	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)	<i>Ave Maria gratia plena</i> (001539)	<i>Ave Maria gratia plena</i> (001539)
M	Speciosa facta es et suavis (206209)	Ave regina caelorum (001542.1)	Alma redemptoris mater (001356) Mater patris et filia (205362) Speciosa facta es et suavis (206209)
Ad Completorium			
A	<i>Dignare me laudare</i> (002217)	Dignare me laudare (002217)	<i>Dignare me laudare</i> (002217)
N	Glorificamus te dei genitrix (002952)	Sub tuum praesidium (005041)	<i>Ecce completa sunt</i> (002498) <i>Speciosa facta es</i> (004988)
Ad Matutinum			
I	In honore beatissimae (001086)	In honore beatissimae (001086)	In honore beatissimae (001086)
In I noct.			
A1.1	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709)	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709)	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709)
A1.2	Sicut myrrha electa (004942)	Sicut myrrha electa (004942)	Sicut myrrha electa (004942)
A1.3	Haec est quae nescivit (003001)	Haec est quae nescivit (003001)	Haec est quae nescivit (003001)
In II noct.			
A2.1	Speciosa facta es (004988)	Specie tua et pulchritudine (004987)	Specie tua et pulchritudine (004987)
A2.2	Dignare me laudare (002217)	Dignare me laudare (002217)	Dignare me laudare (002217)
A2.3	Sicut laetantium (004936)	Sicut laetantium (004936)	Sicut laetantium (004936)
In III noct			
A3.1	Oculi tui sancta dei genitrix (004110)	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)
A3.2	Post partum virgo (004332)	In odorem unguentorum (003261)	In odorem unguentorum (003261)
A3.3	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)	Pulchra es et decora (004418)	Pulchra es et decora (004418)
Ad Laudes			
A1	Sub tuam protectionem (005040)	Post partum virgo (004332)	Post partum virgo (004332)
A2	Hortus conclusus (003137.1)	Oculi tui sancta dei genitrix (004110)	Oculi tui sancta dei genitrix (004110)
A3	Sancta dei genitrix (004699.1)	Maria virgo semper laetare (003708)	Maria virgo semper laetare (003708)
A4	In odorem unguentorum (003261)	Sub tuam protectionem (005040)	Sub tuam protectionem (005040)
A5	Sub tuum praesidium (005041)	Sub tuum praesidium (005041)	Sub tuum praesidium (005041)
B	Ave spes nostra dei genitrix (001546)	Gaude dei genitrix virgo (002920.1)	Gaude dei genitrix virgo (002920.1)
Ad Primam			
A	<i>Hortus conclusus</i> (003137.1)	Hortus conclusus (003137.1)	Hortus conclusus (003137.1)
Ad Tertiam			
A	<i>Sancta dei genitrix</i> (004699.1)	Sancta dei genitrix (004699.1)	Sancta dei genitrix (004699.1)
Ad Sextam			
A	<i>In prole mater</i> (003274)	In prole mater (003274)	In prole mater (003274)
Ad Nonam			
A	<i>Gaude Maria virgo</i> (002924)	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)	Gaude Maria virgo (002924)
Ad II Vesperas			
A1	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709)	Benedicta tu in mulieribus (001709)	
A2	Sicut myrrha electa (004942)	Sicut myrrha electa (004942)	
A3	Haec est quae nescivit (003001)	Haec est quae nescivit (003001)	
A4	Speciosa facta es (004988)	In odorem unguentorum (003261)	
A5	Dignare me laudare (002217)	Pulchra es et decora (004418)	
M	Ave gloriosa dei genitrix (200455.1)	Speciosa facta es et suavis (206209)	

Matins Responsories

	'Soeiro Breviary'	1528 Évora breviary	P-Pm Ms. 368
R1.1 V	Stirps Jesse (007709) Virgo dei genitrix (007709a)	Ave festiva ferculi (600178) Monte Libano (600178a)	Ave festiva ferculi (600178) Monte Libano (600178a)
R1.2 V	Ad nutum domini (006024) Ut vitium virtus (006024a)	Hortus conclusus (601080) Fons hortorum puteus (601080a)	Videte miraculum matris (007869) Haec speciosum forma (007869za)
R1.3 V	Candida virginitas (006262) Quae meruit dominum (006262a)	Solem justitiae regem (007677) Cernere divinum lumen (007677a)	Ave gemma Christi (a06975) Regina caeli palatium (a06975a)
R2.1 V	Virginis electae (602499.1) Coetus caelorum (602499.1a)	Virga dedit florem (a00365) Gaudeat omnis homo (a00365a)	Vulnerasti cor meum (a08511) Quam pulchrae sunt (a08511a)
R2.2 V	Virginibus cunctis (602498.1) Cuius ventre deus jacuit (602498a)	Stirps Jesse (007709) Virgo dei genitrix (007709a)	Ave porta Orientis (a08508) Ante partum virgo manens (a08508a)
R2.3 V	Hortus conclusus (601080) Fons hortorum puteus (601080a)	Stella maris fulget (a06932) Tua virgo prece (a06932a)	O quam pulchra es (a08503) Descendam in hortum (a08503a)
R3.1 V	Ave festiva ferculi (600178) Monte Libano (600178a)	Post partum virgo (007400) Dei genitrix intercede (007400a)	Ad nutum domini (006024) Ut vitium virtus (006024a)
R3.2 V	Virga dedit florem (a00365) Gaudeat omnis homo (a00365a)	Ora pro nobis (601702) Ut digni efficiamur (601702a)	Hortus conclusus (601080) Fons hortorum puteus (601080a)
R3.3 V	Felix valde es (600873.1) Ora pro clero (600873b)	Ad nutum domini (006024) Ut vitium virtus (006024a)	Cella redemptoris signo (a08504) Virgo Maria stella David (a08504a)
		Alternative series	
R1.1 V		O quam pulchra es (a08503) Descendam in hortum (a08503a)	
R1.2 V		Cella redemptoris signo (a08504) Virgo Maria stella David (a08504a)	
R1.3 V		Ave vulnerata charitate (a08506) Sepulti resurrectio (a08506a)	
R2.1 V		Candida virginitas (006262) Quae meruit dominum (006262a)	
R2.2 V		Ego dilecta languedo (a08507) Filiae Jerusalem nuntiate (a08507a)	
R2.3 V		Ave porta Orientis (a08508) Ante partum virgo manens (a08508a)	
R3.1 V1		Stella maris miserans (a08509) Frange cathenas mortis (a08509a)	
R3.2 V1		Ave maria gratia plena (006155) Benedicta tu inter mulieres (006155a)	
R3.3 V1		Pulchrae sunt genae tuae (a08510) Revertere revertere (a08510a)	

Appendix 4. Psalmodic Cursus in the Saturday Office of Our Lady (Three- and Nine-lesson Forms).

Psalm numbers in italics are identified within the psalter section or the daily Hours of the Virgin in the source, on the basis of inference or rubrical indications.

	Three-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i>	Nine-lesson <i>Cantica Canticorum</i>	1528 Évora breviary	<i>P-Pm</i> Ms. 368
Vespers	137, 138, 139, 140, 141	137, 138, 139, 140, 141	<i>137, 138, 139, 140, 141</i>	<i>137, 138, 139, 140, 141</i>
Compline		<i>4, 30, 90, 133</i>	<i>4, 30, 90, 133</i>	<i>4, 30, 90, 133</i>
Matins	94 97, 98, 99	94 8, 18, 23 44, 45, 86 95, 96, 97	94 8, 18, 23 44, 45, 86 95, 96, 97	94 8, 18, 23 44, 45, 86 95, 96, 97
Lauds	92, 99, 62, B, 148-50	92, 99, 62, B, 148-50	<i>92, 99, 62, B, 148-50</i>	92, 99, 62, B, 148-50
Prime	<i>53, 116, 117</i>	<i>53, 116, 117</i>	<i>53, 117, 118:1-32</i>	<i>53, 116, 117</i>
Terce	<i>119, 120, 121</i>	<i>119, 120, 121</i>	<i>118:33-80</i>	118:33-80
Sext	<i>122, 123, 124</i>	<i>122, 123, 124</i>	<i>118:81-128</i>	118:81-128
None	<i>125, 126, 127</i>	<i>125, 126, 127</i>	<i>118:129-76</i>	118:129-76
Vespers II		109, 112, 121, 126, 147	109, 112, 121, 126, 147	